

Unboxing Atlantis

A top-down review of what we know, and don't know, about the Atlantean through
Megalithic Period continents and cities; 36,000 - 2,000 YBP

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ABSTRACT: The existence of foregone lost civilizations is an established fact. The unknown element is to the extent of population coverage, acculturation, architecture, and intercontinental travel. In the last twenty or thirty years several discoveries have re-written the “possibility” of Atlantis and called into question the archaeological lock-out of the topic of submerged and lost/hidden lands.

Key words: Atlantis - Doggerland - Sundaland - Lemuria - Mu - Zealandia - Bermuda - Brasil - Amazon

Synopsis

Atlantis research and the field of Atlantology has become boxed into certain modes of thinking. In this paper, the author intends to reveal the extent of the most common, and a few uncommon, research and thinking about Atlantis, as well as unveil some different ways of thinking about this topic.

Adjacent to this discussion is the HEGEME geology, which is an amalgamation of the most convincing aspects of: EU geology (Hall, Mupp, Thornhill), Electric Star Theory (Jeurgens, Scott), Electroquake Theory (Davidson, Pop), Growing Earth (Yarkovsky, Adams), Expanding Earth (Carey, Heezen), Aether Convection Dynamics (Meyl, Disitinti), and observations of physics, biology, and the laws of energy.¹

The information provided in this paper is not meant to be an exhaustive research, or a final solution to the puzzle, nor to provide a complete - once-and-for-all - answer to the query, "Where is Atlantis?" However, the paper is here to guide past threads through a central choke-throttle^ that both straightens the threads and unravels the knots, as well as offering future clues that could direct future efforts.

The paper is divided into topics as well as confirmed landmasses. A table in the Overview will provide a basically complete explanation as to the method of multiple Atlantean Period and later landmass collapses, utilizing Expanding Plasma-Electromagnetic Cosmology (EPEMC) to leverage maximal use of HEGEME hypothesis to cover the facts of not only Earth plate tectonics, but also celestial bodies seen in the Universe.

The author makes no attempts herein to defend the theories of the above named men. For references see other EPEMC papers, or the works of the above named men directly. Some of their works are stored or referenced directly on the Electric Universe Gateway.

In the final sections the author alludes to very alternative sources of Atlantean myth, as well as to a completely ignored possibility regarding Atlantean search, particularly in the search for culture and traces of an Atlantean age empire.

¹ The Laws of Energy, and an Index of EPEMC terms are found in "Plasma-Electromagnetic Sky," Sf. Careaga, 2018.

Introduction

The study of Atlantis has been, in general, anathema in mainstream archaeology for well over 100 years. Most of the work was in doubt of credibility, as ultimately the linchpin to the entire argument until about 1990 was owing to the words of Plato and has in many ways even today, been dismissed as a fiction.²

“This power came forth out of the Atlantic Ocean, for in those days the Atlantic was navigable; and there was an island situated in front of the straits which are by you called the Pillars of Heracles; the island was larger than Libya and Asia put together, and was the way to other islands, and from these you might pass to the whole of the opposite continent which surrounded the true ocean; for this sea which is within the Straits of Heracles is only a harbour, having a narrow entrance, but that other is a real sea, and the surrounding land may be most truly called a boundless continent. Now in this island of Atlantis there was a great and wonderful empire which had rule over the whole island and several others, and over parts of the continent, and, furthermore, the men of Atlantis had subjected the parts of Libya within the columns of Heracles as far as Egypt, and of Europe as far as Tyrrhenia. This vast power, gathered into one, endeavoured to subdue at a blow our country and yours and the whole of the region within the straits; and then, Solon, your country shone forth, in the excellence of her virtue and strength, among all mankind. She was pre-eminent in courage and military skill, and was the leader of the Hellenes. And when the rest fell off from her, being compelled to stand alone, after having undergone the very extremity of danger, she defeated and triumphed over the invaders, and preserved from slavery those who were not yet subjugated, and generously liberated all the rest of us who dwell within the pillars. But afterwards there occurred violent earthquakes and floods; and in a single day and night of misfortune all your warlike men in a body sank into the earth, and the island of Atlantis in like manner disappeared in the depths of the sea. For which reason the sea in those parts is impassable and impenetrable, because there is a shoal of mud in the way; and this was caused by the subsidence of the island.”³

Why anyone should - at the same time - doubt Plato as study him, is quite confusing. Perhaps they felt he imagined the dialogue with Solon, or Solon's dialogue with the Egyptian Priest.⁴ However, it was, at once, dismissed after so many thousands of years of belief.

Yet, there is also something oddly compelling about the narrative; personal, powerful, and captivating, in a way that one would not usually ascribe to ancient fiction, with some exceptions.⁵ So much so, that, for these last 150 years, avid Atlantologists have scrounged to find Atlantis. Edgar Cayce followers have clung to the several dozen references he has made in his psychic readings (given to various people) wherein he

² <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Atlantis>

³ “Timaeus/Critius”, Plato, 427-347 BCE

⁴ “[Dialogue between Solon and an Egyptian Priest] In the Egyptian Delta, at the head of which the river Nile divides, there is a certain district which is called the district of Sais [...] To this city came Solon, and was received there with great honour; he asked the priests who were most skilful in such matters, about antiquity, and made the discovery that neither he nor any other Hellene knew anything worth mentioning about the times of old. On one occasion, wishing to draw them on to speak of antiquity, he began to tell about the most ancient things in our part of the world-about Phoroneus, who is called “the first man,” and about Niobe; and after the Deluge, of the survival of Deucalion and Pyrrha; and he traced the genealogy of their descendants, and reckoning up the dates, tried to compute how many years ago the events of which he was speaking happened. Thereupon one of the priests, who was of a very great age, said: O Solon, Solon, you Hellenes are never anything but children, and there is not an old man among you. Solon in return asked him what he meant. I mean to say, he replied, that in mind you are all young; there is no old opinion handed down among you by ancient tradition, nor any science which is hoary with age.” ~Plato

⁵ Such as the “Iliad” and “Odyssey,” which, of course, also have interwoven bits of historical fact in what is perhaps the world's first “historical fiction.”

specifically referenced Atlantis.⁶ He even claimed that its people fled, in the primary, to the northwest of North America, becoming the Algonquian speaking peoples, although some went to MesoAmerica, and South America, and Africa, and perhaps became the Basque people of Iberia.⁷

In the mainstream, the majority of those that accepted the possibility of Atlantis posited and focused upon the small Greek isle of Santorini, for it seemed likely to be the result of a vast cataclysmic explosion. Indeed, it was; however, it was not Atlantis, but Akrotiri.⁸ Aside from not fitting the general description of the accepted meaning of “Straits of Gibraltar,” Akrotiri was wiped out only in the 1627 BCE range, and was, instead, likely one of many forms of “Sea Peoples” that populated Mediterranean legends.

However, the mainstream was shocked by the discovery of Akrotiri (1967) on one island that had been considered by many to be a possibility of being Atlantis. It was the first chink in the armor of gridlock against the anthropological pursuit of a lost city of Atlantis. The discovery, since then, of Dvaraka (Dwarka, 1983-1990),⁹ Mauritania (2017),¹⁰ Zealandia (2017),¹¹ and Doggerland¹² (2012)¹³ have placed a new pressure upon archaeology (especially with the growing revelations about Gobekli Tepe, see below) to admit that it has not known about everything after all.

In 2016, it was admitted for the first time, that the majority of scientists now doubt the “Clovis First” theory of peopling of North America, due to the discovery of paleolithic sites that pre-date the Beringia¹⁴ land-bridge (as pre-supposed). In truth, native peoples such as the Haida and the natives of Easter Island, have always maintained that they did not come from Alaska, but arrived by boat, or lived upon a land mass which has since disappeared. The revelations that Beringia indeed was not the only sunken land mass, has all but shocked the world. In the mid 2000’s word first began to leak out about new excavations at Gunung Padang (see below), which had revealed not only an antediluvian age, but a pre Younger Dryas (YD) age, of around 16,000 YBP. It was later extended to 20 kya to 24 kya, one of the oldest megalithic datings on the planet. The legends from Indonesia itself spoke of a time of unmitigated disastrous flooding, which occurred very quickly, and buried most of the world. This was always taken to mean a catastrophic tsunami, due to the proximity of highly active subduction zones.¹⁵ However, upon analysis of deep sea cores, and revelations of ice core samples from Greenland and Antarctica, it was discovered that indeed the ocean had risen hundreds of feet, in a very short period of time.¹⁶ What was once a wide continent of Sundaland was now reef bed, and perhaps up to 60% of the area had disappeared beneath the ocean waves within human memory. This is a very unsettling topic for European archaeology.

As stodgy as they had been about the finding of Troy in 1870’s (and failing to admit that Britains are actually descendants of Troy, as the annals say¹⁷), imagine how difficult it would be for classic studies such as anthropology, Egyptology, Mayanology, etc... to admit there could be an undersea continent with pyramids older than Giza (official dating)! How much more irksome it must have been to learn of Doggerland, proto-Lemuria, *and* Zealandia, confirmed by a far more ‘hard’ science - geology - with plenty of data, in the **same year** (2017). One can only imagine the influx of new pioneering students challenging hoary and grised professors to think ‘outside the box.’

⁶ “Edgar Cayce on Atlantis,” E Cayce, 1968 [3]

⁷ <https://atlantisrisingmagazine.com/article/the-basqueatlantis-connection/>

⁸ [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Akrotiri_\(Santorini\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Akrotiri_(Santorini))

⁹ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Dv%C4%81rak%C4%81>

¹⁰ <http://www.cbc.ca/news/technology/lost-continent-mauritius-indian-ocean-1.3963303>

¹¹ <http://www.geosociety.org/gsatoday/archive/27/3/article/GSATG321A.1.htm>

¹² <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Doggerland>

¹³ <https://www.nationalgeographic.org/maps/doggerland/>

¹⁴ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Beringia>

¹⁵ See: “Boxing Day Tsunami”, 2004 (240,000+ dead)

¹⁶ https://www.giss.nasa.gov/research/briefs/gornitz_09/

¹⁷ <https://folkrealmstudies.weebly.com/brutus-of-troy-first-king-of-britain.html>

In this paper, the author indeed pushes thinking to outside the box. To “unbox” Atlantis means both to open it as a present, and to remove it from the trapped perceptions that have withheld the study for far too long. It is now unavoidable that a discussion must be had. The common internet couch-surfer knows about the little secrets of archaeology like “rongo rongo” script, and Paracas lines, and about sudden and breathtaking discoveries using LiDAR in the Yucatan and Amazon jungles. No longer can such oddities and their OOPArt’s¹⁸ be confined to lost footnotes in thick tomes on dusty shelves in the basement of the annex building at the old campus of Ivy League schools and Oxford, Cambridge, etc...

Overview of Atlantean Period

The Atlantean Period lasted from 36,000 YBP to the sinking of Atlantis, ~12kya and corresponds *precisely* to the beginning of the Younger Dryas and the Tepe Period. The Tepe-Çori¹⁹ Period, is postulated by Hancock,²⁰ Schoch, and Collins to be a stimulus-response to an event which requires a people to remove to a new area, bringing with them the secrets of agriculture, religion, and apparently astronomy. They then dwelt within upper Turkey (at least there) until the sudden end of the YD, upon which they finally purposefully buried their works, perhaps thinking they had angered the gods, and retreated to the underground cities at nearby Derinkuyu and the surrounding area. Some of the cities held perhaps 20,000 people at a time.²¹ It is easy to see that such diggers as was found in the Tepe Period would have made quite easy work of constructing the underground cities therein, and would have been wise enough to use stone doors, and hidden wells to hide from marauders, predators, and other passersby. The question is, are these Atlanteans? If so, are they perhaps from a different region than pre-supposed? Or, is the stronger evidence lying with the common name for the pillars of Gibraltar and the Atlantic Ocean (so named for Atlantis itself)?

The key to understanding the Atlantean Period as a period of its own lies in three facts:

1. Biologically modern humans have existed for at least 240,000 years and may have existed as long as 350,000 years, due to recent adjustments in carbon dating. This means fully potentialized homo sapiens with presumably as much ability for imagination, development, and language as modern humans.
2. Consciously modern humans have origins as long ago as 36,000 YBP. At Lascaux, in France, and in other similar cave sites, evidence of art that has astounded even famed artists covers walls in abundance and clarity of vision. But, more interestingly, cave art depicting fantastical beings, presumed to be gods, spirits, titans, or even aliens thus far (but are actually plasma shapes in the primary) depict a deeper level of consciousness than was previously thought possible.²²
3. The Zodiacs are themselves already depicted upon the thus-far excavated T-stele at Gobekli Tepe. In particular, the lion (leo) is one of the central and oldest stele at the now excavated sites. It just so happens to correspond to separately identified aging of Giza via Schoch²³ and Bauval,²⁴ the former using water erosion of the limestone, and the latter using star charts of Orion from the age of Leo,

¹⁸ “Out of Place Artifacts”

¹⁹ Nevalı Çori, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Nevalı%C4%B1_%C3%87ori

²⁰ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=_nNq2O3-vAo

²¹ <https://roadtrippers.com/stories/this-ancient-underground-city-once-held-20-000-people>

²² Is it these roots which, planted for another 6,000 years (longer than from our time to Egypt), make it possible for early modern man to construct the Bosnian Pyramids but digging and making proto-concrete mudstone, and laying it in beautiful layers and geometric slabs upon a shaped mountain? Similarly, to repeat such behavior at Gunung Padang really challenges our thoughts about early modern man.

²³ <http://www.robertschoch.net/Geological%20Evidence%20Sphinx%202000.htm>

²⁴ http://www.robertbauval.co.uk/articles/articles_guest/valioct1.html

which the Sphinx most clearly originally was a lion.²⁵ This confirms the age of Gobekli tepe carbon dating to be the age of leo (at the latest), during the Younger Dryas period.²⁶

From this, the narrative becomes simple, but full of important gaps. To understand the first part, one must have faith in early modern man based upon the obvious genius of post agricultural and industrial modern man. It is obvious to all the progress of mankind from the Renaissance forward, and in certain periods of human history, such as early Egypt, Sumer, Han and Tang China, the Mongol and Roman empires, the Age of Exploration, and the Mayans. However, there is a lingering doubt among certain scientists, scholars, theologians, and common folk that mankind is, in fact, quite capable of developing new and unique ideas on his own. It must be stated, also, that most people, scientist or not, have no concept of time or spatial dimensions in a practicable sense. So a few extra thousand years tacked on seems to mean little, when in fact, much should be expected to have occurred in that space, as much has occurred in the last four periods (Megalithic, Transition, Religious, and Scientific; covering the ages of Aries and Pisces).

Even factoring in the acceleration due to progressive evolution of development, technology, and culture, the fact is that there is room for successive periods of rapid growth that was cut off ere it became as civilized as we see at current time. The fact that depictions of power devices such as Crooke's tubes²⁷ on hieroglyphs, amongst other odd glyphs, and obvious use of power tools, including 19' saws²⁸ with Ruthenium compounds in them, suggests that the only difference in their abilities and ours was the presence (or lack of in their case) of plentiful hydrocarbon supplies, which as mentioned in previous works by the author, came from Venus' comet tail.²⁹

This has a profound effect upon our chronology, but also solves some of the dilemmas of the mainstream by a) ridding ourselves of the need of ancient aliens or other distracting pseudoscientific hypotheses and b) allowing for the explanation of how cultures seemed to "degrade" over time, and produce less impressive megaliths and architecture. The answer is simple. It was built in a previous period, which was destroyed due to large scale catastrophes,³⁰ and the later cultures tried to mimic them but due to living beneath the Earth for a few thousand years, and reverting back to nature, much was forgotten. This is admitted to in most cultures, from the Inca to the Egyptians. Many techniques were so lost that we cannot even repeat use of them today.³¹

The analysis therefore yields a simple result: people make progress, but nature cuts them off. However, could there have been a time that preceded the YD where mankind was able to make thorough progress, unhindered, for a long period of time? It stands to reason that, if the Zep Tepi solar configuration under Kronus-Saturn were undisturbed long enough, that if the system could grow Earth by up to 2-3x its ancient

²⁵ The theory that the Sphinx was first a lion, then re-carved to have a pharaonic head, receives greatest support from the fact that the head is so much smaller than the body, by proportion. It is proposed that the body was buried in the sands, and the head was all that was visible when the re-figuring took place. <https://grahamhancock.com/templer1/>

²⁶ <http://myblog.robertbauval.co.uk/2014/12/22/the-age-of-leo/>

²⁷ "Giza Power Plant," C Dunn; seems absurd but for the lack of soot found in temples such as Karnak and Giza

²⁸ "Lost Technologies of Ancient Egypt", C Dunn

²⁹ Ambrosia or mana, which fell from the upper stratosphere and was reported across the desert belt cultures. See "Worlds in Collision," I Velikovsky, 1950

³⁰ To an ant, a spilled gallon of water is a deluge and catastrophe. Even modern volcanology relies upon a VEI scaling system to describe eruption sizes, and so the uniformitarian scales are, after all, broken up by staccato changes; often violent and sudden. Sometimes local, sometimes regional, sometimes national or international. The Boxing Day tsunami claimed 240,000 lives in over a dozen countries, but had almost no effect in the majority of the world. That was only an 8.4 earthquake. A VEI8, 9, or 10 event can drastically change the course of evolution worldwide, much less an X20 CME, a celestial collision, or a large comet impact! There are even reports of massive earthquakes due to prolonged supernova brightening the sky, inducing electroquakes. (Meyl, Davidson)

³¹ Such as precise cutting of certain shapes of stone, or the lifting of megaliths, especially exceeding 70 tons. See: Baalbak megaliths (Temple of Jupiter)

diameter to current diameter, that after all there was enough energy to sustain accelerated evolutionary growth of early mankind as well.

Such a system, reputedly, had only wet and dry seasons, and remained in a decent temperature year round. There was, it seems, rapid change later which drove mankind into the south due to blizzards and terrible winter. The memory of this change extends to India, China, Scandinavia, and Iran where it has been written down. But prior to this, perhaps there was quite a different climate worldwide. Evidence for this is easily found in the far north of Scotland at Orkney where balmy climates enabled an advanced stone-house building culture to emerge 6,000 YBP.³²

It seems quite logical to extend such abilities to develop in warmer climates backwards when we know, in fact, that the Sahara (for example) was a savannah paradise,³³ with three massive lakes,³⁴ only 10-12 kya. Stories in Sumerian and Babylonian myth of an Ed-in are mirrored in Biblical tales, presumably believed by Semites because they were displaced peoples that came from the Sahara or Mesopotamian regions to Egypt during the YD catastrophe. Considering the size of the Sahara and Arabian deserts, it is tempting to include the Saharan savannah in this treatise.³⁵

What is not clear to us is whence man came and where he went, and why (other than for following game, or due to catastrophe after catastrophe). The movements of mankind are shrouded in mystery. Aforementioned speculation of actual precision has proven to be fallacious and misleading, as mtDNA testing has shown that ancestry is far more complicated than previously imagined.³⁶ For example, a native New Zealander might have Maori, Persian, and Peruvian blood in their ancestry.³⁷

To make it worse, when a site such as Nevali Cori is purposefully covered,³⁸ or a site like Gobekli Tepe or Dvaraka or Gunung Padang is purposefully stopped from excavation by archaeological and political authorities, crucial data is not only not uncovered, it is forgotten and even buried (ironically).

It is entirely unclear, for example, which bodies of water existed at any given period, and what the size of the bodies of water were, because of the changes in ice, sea level, and climate. The following three figures may help illustrate the problem:

³² <https://www.theguardian.com/science/2012/oct/06/orkney-temple-centre-ancient-britain>

³³ <https://www.livescience.com/4180-sahara-desert-lush-populated.html>

³⁴ <https://insider.si.edu/2010/12/ancient-megalake-discovered-beneath-sahara-desert/>

³⁵ The Sahara and the “desert belt” will be the subject of a separate paper “The World of the Red Dust”

³⁶ <https://www.sciencealert.com/oldest-hominins-could-have-lived-in-europe-instead-of-africa-claims-new-study>

³⁷ “Under the Carpet” and “Skeletons in the Cupboard”

³⁸ In Kentucky alone, dozens of crucial Allegheni and Hopewellian sites may have been buried to make way for reservoirs built by the TVA and Army Corps of Engineers, prior to their excavations.

Figure 1 - 65 Million Years of Climate Change credit: Robert A. Rohde

Figure 2 - 16,000 years of Climate Change

Figure 3 - Ice Age Temperatures for 450,000 years

Figure 1 makes it clear that climate change has drastically altered and lowered since the age of the dinosaurs, and the Young Earth (YE) eras. It also makes it clear that whatever wobble to our solar orbit around our then stellar host (and possible creator), began in the last millions of years. It is possible that Jupiter at this time first entered conjunction with Saturn and thus began the collinear polar configuration (see EPEMC [1]). It could also have been the mark of the loss of Saturn's plasma sheath, due to such a change in solar system electrical circuit. It is not known; these are only speculations

Figure 2 demonstrates the sudden and marked changes in temperature, and therefore ice volume and consequently sea level since the YD. The sudden rise in temperature at the end of YD is as drastic as the descent into it, and must have been accompanied by major disturbances which shook Tepe Period peoples to their core. However, conditions were obviously not ripe for mankind's return to agricultural prominence, as Sumeria did not emerge for another 5,000+ years. Presumably this regrowth period was hampered by the sudden cooldown 8,200 YBP. The strange descent into the YD was preceded by a steep rise in temperature. Such a spike must be indicative of orbital changes, or tilt, or both. It is unlikely to be the precession of the equinoxes, as that is generally accounted for in the average peaks and valleys of the graph in both figures. Atmospheric composition could not have changed so drastically, and it is doubtful that a volcano would cause a spike in temperature, though it has been argued to cause the fall. The author maintains, however, that this event was, perhaps more catastrophic than that. It was potentially as severe as the sudden near collision with the Moon, and a worldwide violent gale³⁹ and super-tsunamis,⁴⁰ constituting the original Great Flood myths of many peoples.⁴¹ However, this event may have also come later. This is the difficulty of unraveling the Atlantean and Archaic periods, and wedged between them, the Tepe Period.

Figure 3 shows us the spikes of ice ages, to be sure. But more importantly it shows us the improving conditions from 35,000 to 30,000 YBP and 23,000 to now (despite YD). Such conditions would, undoubtedly spur on sudden developments.

The hypothesis then follows, that during this time, beginning but slowly, mankind began to build megalithic architecture, in honor of the gods.[2] As to the extent of this, it is not known. There is some thought that other than the Bosnian "Pyramid of the Sun" and other shaped land masses, which have strange,

³⁹ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=l-e_jfv-kGU

⁴⁰ <https://www.thunderbolts.info/wp/2018/03/31/sputtering-canyons-part-3/>

⁴¹ Pre Age of Taurus myths, as opposed to the Noah/Ziusudra myth of the Bible <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ziusudra>

documented alignments to the North pole and stars,⁴² that the Mexican “Pyramid of the Sun” (Teotihuacan)⁴³ and the smallest of the Great Pyramids were first designed. Options for the Giza construction seem most optimal at the age of Leo, or, due to typical wobble of the zodiacs, to another constellation, such as Draco. However, though it cannot be known based on star charts alone, geological weathering and various dating techniques may yield for us very reliable windows that can then be compared with star charts, perhaps via supercomputer simulation.

Hopefully, in the sections that follow, the lack of evidence ceases to be a burden but instead a call for more research. After all, how many feet of soil and sand was Troy buried beneath, after only a few thousand years? There could be dozens of cities and sites waiting to be unearthed mere hundreds of feet below the surface in much of the world, or, perhaps beneath the reef beds. In the very next section, the author will unpack our first gift, Gobekli Tepe, and what specific mysteries it houses that can teach us about the Atlantean and Tepe Periods.

Gobekli Tepe - the lost Tepe Period

When Solon spoke to Plato, there was no mention of a Silver Age. The Egyptian priest merely spoke that all philosophy, math, and science had already been discovered before, in man’s Golden Age. Presumably he had had access as an acolyte to some of the ancient manuscripts, or copies of, or had read upon the stone glyph covered walls at Karnak truths which have even to now, become lost. It is known, for example, that the Sumerians used a base 60 math system and even adamantly insisted the Earth’s solar orbit was precisely 360 days. That this was later changed to 350 days by the Romans either points to the earlier greater precision of a superior civilization or the difficulty our Roman cultural forebears had in matching the precision of the ancients without telescopes. Of course, it has also been offered as proof of solar system changes by proponents of Velikovskianism. However, regardless of meaning, it is clear that the math was more advanced than that of the Greeks or Romans, who used cumbersome numerals even while in India and Persian advanced mathematics was already in common use.

The creation of strange OOPArt technologies, such as the Antikythera Mechanism, or the Baghdad Battery, in such remote days which were not rediscovered for thousands of years by modern archaeology, also points to a possibility that indeed the Egyptian Priest could have been right, and not simply boastful of his nation. But, more to our curiosity, why is there no mention of a Silver Age, preceding Greece and Babylon? There isn’t even a mention of Sumer, although undoubtedly Plato knew of it and its classical wisdom⁴⁴ and antiquity.

This will be surely thought of as passing strange, given the love Greeks had for Egyptian culture. Indeed the relationship of the entire region, and the likely kinship of the ancient pharaohs with Europeans,⁴⁵ it seems very odd for there to be no mention of Sumer or of the Tepe people.

That is, unless one considers first the secrecy of the Tepe-Çori peoples, and their remote antiquity, as well as the Sumerian myths about Tiamat, and the 8,200 YBP cataclysm. It is entirely plausible that the remote society of Gobekli Tepe, and surrounding cultures, spoke root languages that went not south but north, following the warming periods, into the Caucasus, Balkans, and eventually to Scandinavia becoming the Norse, Russian and Sami peoples.

⁴² <http://www.gizaforhumanity.org/scientific-analysis-of-the-bosnian-valley-of-the-pyramids/>

⁴³ <https://uncoveredhistory.com/mexico/teotihuacan/teotihuacan-pyramid-of-the-sun/>

⁴⁴ The libraries of Akkad and Uruk have revealed much via clay tablet decoding of “cuneiform” script. Sumer was responsible for much, if not most, of what makes western society western, as opposed to middle eastern or oriental. They were, in many ways, downright occidental.

<https://www.ancienthistorylists.com/mesopotamia-history/top-11-inventions-and-discoveries-of-mesopotamia/>

⁴⁵ <https://www.independent.co.uk/news/science/archaeology/ancient-egyptians-europeans-related-claims-a7763866.html>

The remoteness of mountain peoples, such as the Basque, or Balkans, or in the Orient the Qiang and Tibetans, informs us that when groups of peoples remove themselves from a region, they are (considering the evolution of languages), all but extinct. To this day, for example, although many Lebanese claim ancestry of the Phoenicians, there is no proof that they were a separate ethnicity. There are many such examples of cultural identities (and languages) from the Middle East and Jordanian region alone, much less to say about remote areas of Eastern and Northern Europe, Asia, Siberia, and of course Africa.⁴⁶

What is it specifically, that Gobekli Tepe can teach us? First, there are, much to the surprise (and nearly completely dismissed as a site altogether, with a much later date) and chagrin of archaeologists, forms of language and culture, and even religion upon the T-stele of Gobekli Tepe (and buried underwater Nevali Cori). The language thereon is only partially decipherable to modern linguists, but in some stele speaks clearly of impending comets and disasters. More interestingly for future discussions, there are certain glyphs (such as the “handbag” glyph), which are shared with other cultures worldwide which can support either a plasmaglyph hypothesis and/or Atlantean genesis.⁴⁷

Another interesting facet is that although Gobekli Tepe was occupied for thousands of years, it had successive waves of burial and re-formation of C-shaped “temple” compounds, with differing forms of T-stele in each, indicating some form of complex star charting, zodiacal or other astronomical study.⁴⁸ This most reflects, if anything, the oral traditions of southern India, and aboriginal Australia, which maintain quite insistently that their cultures are between 40,000 and 60,000 years old. Considering the unapproachable length of the orally maintained Mahabharata (over 100,000 stanzas), if the story is a form of astronomical literature or record via drama, then there is some basis for such assertions. Both cultures remain, as it were, near to some of the newly found or asserted continents (Lemuria and Sundaland and Zealandia). It is, therefore, entirely possible that these culture share in common an oral tradition of astronomical recordkeeping much akin to the Dogon, both literal and taken very seriously, but a record of the ‘alien’ gods.

Regardless, the T-stele at Gobekli Tepe utilize titanisque and zodiacal designs⁴⁹ that are foreign to the Persian system, yet related in intricate ways, generally via animal “totems” (for lack of a better word). There appears also (in the less than 20% excavation of entire site) to be an entire system of cosmology in place, describing the origins of mankind, and the destructions.⁵⁰ As mentioned before, the site was buried on purpose, after which the Tepe period ended and the underground city “Archaic Period” began, about which we know very little, in the main. We are far more comfortable and familiar with the succeeding Megalithic Period, although we know, for all intents and purposes, very little about it as well.⁵¹

The site has plenty of other lessons as well, such as observation of early human logistics, engineering, community organization, and of course agriculture (or a form of early industry). The site is clearly well organized, purposeful, maintained, and reflects higher consciousness (far more than similarly compared sites like Stonehenge which by comparison is naught by random plinths) of modern humans. Yet, where did the development come from? It is, if record is to be believed, as if they sprang out of holes in the ground.

To put it in perspective consider this chronogram:

⁴⁶ One example being the Dogon people, who retain clear cultural ties to the Middle Kingdom of Egypt, yet remain far away in Sudan.

⁴⁷ The “handbag” glyphs, found in Peru, Mexico, Sumer, Egypt, and Gobekli Tepe all appear to be in use as a form of technology, rather than as a constellation alone (as compared, say, to the concentric circle glyph) <http://www.ancient-origins.net/artifacts-other-artifacts/what-mysterious-handbag-seen-ancient-carvings-across-cultures-and-021191> and https://rgdn.info/en/chto_nesut_bogi_v_sumochkah

⁴⁸ <http://www.ancient-origins.net/news-history-archaeology/archaeologists-find-12000-year-old-pictograph-gobekli-tepe-003441>

⁴⁹ <https://grahamhancock.com/collinsa3/>

⁵⁰ <http://maajournal.com/Issues/2017/Vol17-1/Sweatman%20and%20Tsikritsis%2017%281%29.pdf>

⁵¹ Consider Stonehenge, a relatively simple megalithic site upon which hundreds of careers are based, due to the overwhelming mystery which surrounds the site; a mystery that continues to confound scientists and rewrite history, even after 200+ years of continuous study, as well as thousands of years of reverence by bards and scholars.

30 kya

<25kya|20-24kya>

12kya-9kya

8kya-7kya

5kya-->

Consider the massive gaps in between, of which Gunung Padang can hardly be thought to be a factor due to the incredible distance of Sundaland.⁵² Instead, the nearest “ancestor” found would be Bosnian, which, considering climate factors could have moved southeast. However, the author wishes to postulate that there is a more likely nearby source of cultural influence, to be discussed in a later section.

The main point to consider here is that Gobekli Tepe teaches us that we do not really know anything about the early periods of modern mankind, what they were capable of, and how their developments influenced our own (speaking as Western civilization, and perhaps wider, if the Tower of Babylon and linguistic analysis of ancient Chinese scripts are to be believed).⁵³

Final Lessons of the Mayans and Amazonians

In May of 2016, teenager William Gadoury shocked the world, galvanized it, and irked a whole lot of classical Mayanologists by first aligning cities to constellations and then daring to use satellite and LiDAR imagery to “find” lost cities.⁵⁴ What he did was inform the public of a little known secret kept only to select communities of archaeologists, and he circumnavigated the traditional routes of fame and notoriety. The jealousy notwithstanding, it was revealing to the state of discovery, and if anything, a foreshadowing of a more important discovery to follow in early 2018, when it was announced that a megalopolis was discovered via LiDAR of Mayan cities that housed between two and ten *million* people.⁵⁵

The news of this discovery made more waves in the news than even the possible discovery of pyramids beneath the waves of Bermuda.⁵⁶ Mostly because it was believed, but also because it was fairly shocking to consider that such a lost city could appear above water, so long after the invention of cameras, airplanes, satellite photography and the internet.

This follows upon the growing news stories of both the discovery of new Nazca and Paracas lines in Peru **and** the emergence of what can only be termed as an unknown empire of Amazonia.⁵⁷ The earthworks revealed at first by deforestation and afterwards by intrepid and excited explorers can only be described as refreshing and breathtaking. The fact that they mirror the earthworks of the Ohio River Valley both in size and geometries bolsters both the diffusionist and PEMC hypotheses about earthworks, suggesting both contact *and* astronomical origins. However, at this time nothing but the most superficial aspects is known about either Amazonia or this lost city of the Yucatan. More will be discussed later about Amazonia.

The lesson, therefore, resurfaces, as if from the very pages of Sir Arthur Conan Doyle, “It is a capital mistake to theorize before one has data. Insensibly one begins to twist facts to suit theories, instead of theories to suit facts.” Mainstream archaeology and anthropology has mistakenly done such pseudoscience, and will pay dearly for it in reputation. Yet they shall recover, for these discoveries will surely stir the hearts and minds of young people for many decades to come, and they will continue to challenge antiquated opinions that were made ‘sine merito.’

However, if one were to speculate about the end of the Atlantean Period, a viable mechanism would be necessary for covering all the facts of continental removal that supported the testimony of Plato/Solon as well as modern geology, without necessarily invalidating plate tectonics or standard volcanology. Luckily, EPENC

⁵² Even with Diffusionist paradigm, it seems hardly tenable that a plinth and clay stone age culture would sail to Turkey.

⁵³ “God in Ancient China” <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=DA-AkJzpKmg>

⁵⁴ <https://news.nationalgeographic.com/2016/06/lost-maya-city-mexico-william-gadoury-satellite-discovery-archaeology/>

⁵⁵ <http://www.cbc.ca/news/technology/mayan-pyramids-1.4519863>

⁵⁶ <https://overmanwarrior.blog/2012/06/27/tongue-of-the-ocean-pyramids-discovered-in-the-bahamas-the-roots-of-atlantis/> and <http://www.dailymail.co.uk/sciencetech/article-4997240/Pyramids-spotted-bottom-Atlantic-ocean.html>

⁵⁷ Rumors of El Dorado have yet to even resurface and catch up to this discovery!

has within its arsenal three such additional theorems, as well as the merit of plasma-electromagnetic cosmology which itself provides for an entirely enhanced view of the Earthen system.⁵⁸

Mechanism of Crustal Collapse, the hidden dangers of Hot Spots and Earthspots

Before continuing into the individual continents themselves, it is first necessary to explain how entire landmasses may shift or change. To explain that, however, requires an upgrade to modern geology and plate tectonics (PT), which remain perfectly viable within their uniformitarian parameters, when reasonable (such as karst formation of caves, or wind-made sandstone arches or water-carved limestone arches, as opposed to those formed by ion diffusion and sputtering discharge, such as in the canyonlands of Utah).⁵⁹

The following table will lay out the upgrades to PT, HE, and EGE which maintain the law of conservation of mass-energy as well as follow one of the dictates of the law of evolution/change⁶⁰, both of which are subject to the law of energy.⁶¹

Table 1 - Summary of EPEMC Stellar-Earth Circuit Geology

The EGE exists as part of a stellar electromagnetic network.	These magnetic tunnels and filaments are owing to Birkeland Currents	The HE is formed by a very thin series of layers that act as a transceiver of stellar and planetary signals
The solar system (SS) functions as an effective electrical circuit.	The planets and other bodies have varying levels of conductance, resistance, capacitance, and inductance	The upper layers connect via magnetic tunnels and stellar winds; the inner spongier mantle is where heated materials circulate (due to polarized molecules)
The modular SS forms part of a galactic “pearl necklace” effect, which is overall a greater galactic and intergalactic circuit of energy transfer	The SS functions as an organ, and each planet or satellite, as an organelle, and each layer in them is a tissue, with a specific function in the solar circuit (SC).	The crust is the junction layer, it is a thin permeable membrane of highly reactive chemical substances and unstable molecules which perform electro-magnetic transfer tasks, including accumulation and dispersion.
The sun behaves as a transistor, but exfoliates fused material both in long periods and suddenly, if fused (heavy) material accumulates interiorly to the Hollow Sun (HS)	The sun is affected by a series of analog signals from other stars, which behave in parallel	The parallel galactic stars then act in series with other components (such as nebulae, clusters, quasars, etc...) and galaxies
The Earth behaves as a stellar	It receives energy in both poles,	The cosmic rays, particularly

⁵⁸ The Mantle, and plate movements remain, however the contents of the outer and inner core do change, and add more complex chemistry, as well as joining Earth to a greater stellar/solar system electrical grid or circuit. “Hollow Earth” (HE) and “Expanding/Growing Earth” (EGE) evolve into a new model of water-filled Earth which grows via neutrinos and cosmic rays and the production of more water.

⁵⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZZB4-JEU-eQ>

⁶⁰ That which is not growing is dying; stagnation is decay; homeostasis is always temporary and forced; all objects that are born will eventually die, disintegrate, and only re-emerge with re-configuration. Ergo to be existent dictates growth.

⁶¹ Energy is abundant but sparsely concentrated, except as mass.

transformer	but grows as a fruit on a vine	neutrinos, are trapped within the water-producing core
The EGE is in production of EZ-water and other heavy water due to solar winds	The HE holds the water, which is heavy and captures neutrino and other radiation, generating heat	The heat and pressure is augmented by voltage “tension”; the Earth is a spherical capacitor.
The PT is due to crystallization properties and thermoelectric convection	Convection pressure is maintained by current storage (induction)	Crystallization enables piezoelectric circulating along “leylines” much as any circuit diagram
PT movement happens slowly relative to humans, but can accelerate due to thermomagnetic changes in the Field	Crustal bubbling occurs at rapid convection “hotspots” which are places of increased electromagnetic tunnel pressure	Joints between active PT may also influence the Field and release heat and thermoelectromagnetic energy to stabilize the transformer
As the transformer grows, its C,L,R. N1/2 properties will modify	Convections may heat up or shut down as mantle material shifts	Such shifts produce minor wobble in Earth tilt
Earth tilt is also decreasing due to stellar re-configuration	Tidal lock and lunar influence continue to generate convection, but decrease as the moon moves away from Earth	Stellar cycles have a predictable and uniformitarian effect upon solar bodies
Hotspot bubbling may increase the space beneath crusts, introducing large oceanic cavities of heavy water	Heavy water pockets temporarily give buoyancy to the crust, but cracks do form, leaking water through crystalline minerals and changing water to “normal form”	Changes in stellar flow, such as new stars, novae, and comets will alter the growth rate and act as trigger events
When bubbles pop, the weight of the crust may squeeze the rest of the water through causing slow collapse.	When hot spots explode, the collapse may be sudden and violent.	When rifts form, Earth spots (EM tunnels with the sun) may move over them causing sudden tearing movements, precipitating violent earthquakes beyond PT norms.
When the HE is heated up, it will undergo a rapid cooldown internally as high pressure ejecta precipitate to the surface and cover the planet. May be coeval with stellar exfoliation	When the EGE growth rate exceeds the PT subduction rate by a high degree, tears in the rifts may create new megavolcanoes and hotspots, and baby continents.	Heavier continental crusts will dominate thinner crusts, but remain vulnerable to upper atmospheric charge
The SC interacts with the galactic circuit, but the active sun (Sol) dominates the plasma distribution in the SS	The larger gas giants (GG) have greater field effects, which have in turn significant effects on the EGE	Mountains may rise or fall suddenly, as canyons may form suddenly, in the interaction of SC components discharge, and electrogravity uplifts or pushes down crystal lattice formations
The HE inner core may in fact also be a fusion reactor; it is not known	The spongy mantle may also, in fact, produce hydrocarbons, it is not known	The movement of charge distribution in the SC, EGE, and GC’s overall conforms to the laws

In short, the Earth is in a dynamic, active relationship with the moon, sun, and planets, which will cause continual changes to the Earth's size and chemistry, and general environment. As it seeks to keep equilibrium, the Field constantly adapts (analog) to maintain a steady pulsating signal. This creates bubbling and cracking in brittle mica-thin (relative to the mantle) crustal layers of the Earth, and leads to sudden uprise and potentially equally sudden collapses.

Photo: Iceland (false color) geology from Satellite View, a hotspot primed for collapse; Credit: geology.com⁶²

⁶² Many people do not know that in fact on Iceland there are active, lava spewing volcanoes, located beneath sheets of ice.

Doggerland

The first, and perhaps most accepted thus far, of the new continents is Doggerland.⁶³ It is accepted to have sunk due to rising sea levels. However, the rise in sea levels only accounts for a small amount of the collapse. The remainder is due to weight, and currently is blamed upon weak seabeds (as is the Bahamas). However, as is explained in Table 1, it is to be expected that as the crust collapses, water levels will also increase, as a bubble of water beneath the crust seeps through the permeable membrane and forms pockets of heavier, toxic water at the bottom of the ocean.⁶⁴

Such “deuterated” water is the product of chemico-fusion pressures beneath the crust in the mantle and outer core. The water is quite toxic, and yet, has many of the properties of life-giving organic compounds and minerals, which have been found to help form the basis of evolutionary genesis⁶⁵ and strange lifeforms.⁶⁶

Doggerland is, of course, described in mythical accounts of the Norse and Britains. It was a much maligned theory of a land until its discovery in 2012 via deep sea core exploration. Since then footprints and fossils have been unearthed which support Archaic period inhabitants.⁶⁷

More interesting is that theories range of its collapse from anywhere in the Atlantean Period to the 8,200 YBP mark or even in the near Megalithic Period 6,000 YBP.⁶⁸ Clearly, then, this could be the ostensible home of the Tepe Period people, especially if they retreated south due to the cold in the beginning of the YD.

This makes Doggerland the *most official* of the accepted lost continents, in that it is, after all, near and dear to the hearts of Western civilization’s archaeology and *almost* in the Atlantic Ocean proper. However, a number of problems arise with this being *the* proposed location of Atlantis, and thus why most take to calling it the “Atlantis of Britain.”

First is the location is very far north, and does not seem to conform to Solon’s story. Secondly no proposed Golden Age civilization is proposed to have inhabited the island, only paleolithic hunter-gatherers that followed ice age megafauna to the land, and then retreated as the land shrank. Finally, the fact that it happened over thousands of years and not “in a single day and night” have basically excluded this continental island from further consideration by both Atlantologists and mainstream archaeologists.

It is, however, incredibly important for the same reasons as Amazonia and the lost cities of the Yucatan: it has taught archaeology to open its mind and search beneath the sea waves. Since Doggerland, the expectations of finding sunken seabeds (that is: formerly land and even forest) have drastically increased.

⁶³

<https://www.telegraph.co.uk/news/earth/environment/archaeology/11836627/British-Atlantis-archaeologists-begin-exploring-lost-world-of-Doggerland.html>

⁶⁴ <https://www.mnn.com/earth-matters/wilderness-resources/stories/bizarre-lake-under-sea-discovered-kills-whatever-swims-there>

⁶⁵ <https://www.whoj.edu/news-release/methane-formation>

⁶⁶ <http://ocean.si.edu/ocean-news/microbes-keep-hydrothermal-vents-pumping>

⁶⁷ <http://www.ancient-origins.net/news-history-archaeology/7000-year-old-forest-and-footprints-uncovered-atlantis-britain-005913>

⁶⁸ <http://eden-saga.com/en/underwater-archaeology-northsea-doggerbank-doggerland-second-atlantis.html>

Sundaland

Sundaland is, by far, the most anticipated of archaeological playgrounds, outside of Amazonia. Of the list provided, it is expected to yield many more earthen-made pyramids within coastline. However, there are several challenges to the exploration of Sundaland. Although the depth of most of it is not great, the storms and volcano prone area present great danger to explorers. This is unlikely to deter Asiatic treasure hunters, especially closer to Thailand, Singapore, Jakarta, and Australia, but will present some difficulties in validating 3D sonographs and bathymetry performed in the region. The currents are strong, and the earthquakes sporadic and violent. Most of the area is known for either a tourists' paradise or a terrorist and pirate breeding ground.

While much of archaeology anticipates the region's great promise, the actual success of exploration may depend upon military charting and continued mapping of the sea floor over time. Until the Boxing Day tsunami, most of the region was not even checked for tsunami warnings. The Indian Ocean and Oceania will provide also a great many hazards to sea vessels from typhoons and vortices to coral reefs and pirates.

However, with the promise of Gunung Padang on shore, and related Pohnpei (see Mu) the legends of Polynesians⁶⁹ regarding volcanic explorers that sailed the seas gives hope to the finding of lost civilizations that are vast in number, populations, and potentially cultural wealth that is far out of the expected norm.

Figure 4 - Sundaland

⁶⁹ <http://www.mythencyclopedia.com/Pa-Pr/Polynesian-Mythology.html>

Gunung Padang

In particular, Gunung Padang (active: 22 kya - 7 kya) is the most promising site in the quest to understand Sundaland culture and religion. At present, there are many obstacles. A number of extremely pedantic archaeologists⁷⁰ that have not physically excavated the site have lobbied political forces within the Indonesian Presidency to stop excavations by revoking previously given permits (by a political rival, since deposited). This is despite the excellent ground penetrating radar proof(s) of the existence of either a man made chamber or a magma chamber, either of which proves to be incredible.

The site is maligned by superstitions of the local folk, fed by migrations of New Age energy seekers that bring with them hosts of expectations and also genuine, innocent curiosity which at times aggravates locals who feel the site is pure and spiritual, and not to be disrespected. This has made cross-cultural barriers difficult to overcome, and led to some local support of the resistance to scientific exploration, even by Indonesians.⁷¹

The site is incredibly archaic, and most definitely (according to carbon dating and other methods) from the Atlantean period. It is the primary proof of the theorem that mankind can, given a warm climate, make progress towards organization and worship, and building of megalithic structure pre-Egypt. The site is, for all intents and purposes, the perfect proving ground for catastrophist-diffusionist theory. Where did the people come from? Where did they go? Why did they leave?

There is some speculation that the mountain was a volcano,⁷² or was an altar for a nearby volcano-god, which, like Mt. Ararat or Vesuvius, exploded suddenly and violently, and unleashed hellish fury and pyroclastic oblivion upon the inhabitants of Sundaland.

The entire believability of the site hinges upon not primarily the dating, but upon the naturalness and orientation of basalt columns in the building of the step pyramid. If one believes Schoch, they are rearranged by man (as at Pohnpei), and later abandoned by an extinct religious culture that gave up the religion. The date for such attempts is relatively modern, within the last three millenia. However, if one believes the earlier layers of the step pyramid are man made, even surrounding the volcano god, then the dates become exceedingly ancient. The mainstream counters that these dates are due to volcanic activity.

However, the lead investigator, Danny Hillman is also a seismologist and has been on site for many years. There appears to be little motive for falsifying data, and much effort made to utilize the latest scientific techniques. Despite poor archaeology practices early on (such as using heavy equipment and military personnel), the site has yielded great quantities of data, and as mentioned previously, local legends abound as to the antiquity and hallowness of the site. It seems most likely, at this point, that within 20 years the excavations will continue and yield more intriguing results and teach us how to find new Sundaland sites.

⁷⁰ <http://www.thejakartapost.com/news/2014/09/24/archaeologists-slam-excavation-gunung-padang-site.html>

⁷¹ <https://www.skepticink.com/lateraltruth/2017/09/23/gunung-padang-last-open-letter-danny-hilman/>

⁷² <https://www.skepticink.com/lateraltruth/2016/11/12/pyramids-pt-2-gunung-padang/>

Mauritius/Lemuria

Lemuria⁷³ (called Kumari Kandam or Kumarika Khanda by Tamil purists)⁷⁴ is, like Atlantis, supposedly an ancient hypothesis of a lost land. It was the name proposed by scientist Philip Sclater in 1864, to explain the appearance of rare lemurs upon southern India and Sri Lanka, but nowhere else but their home in Madagascar. Of course, the main argument against this is that travelers could have brought them to Tamil India, however, it is quite impossible for primates to evolve separately and become lemurs in both places at once.

The other, incredibly plausible, but not favored explanation is the existence of a sunken continent. This receives favor from the Tamil (and the lemurs), in that they propose that Gondwana did not break apart, but sank beneath the ocean as Solon has said. However, the assertion being that the Pillars of Heracles are not at Gibraltar, but instead at the end of the Red Sea as shown in Figure 5

Figure 5 - Exit to the Red Sea to Gulf of Aden = Pillars of Heracles?

⁷³ [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Lemuria_\(continent\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Lemuria_(continent))

⁷⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kumari_Kandam

This theory carries with it several distinct advantages. First, the proximity to Egypt. Second, the discovery of Mauritia, a lost continent below the islands of Mauritius⁷⁵ (thereby reviving the discussion). Third, the origins of the Deluge potentially being a massive comet striking near to Madagascar.⁷⁶ Fourth, the fact that it isn't known for sure that the Greeks would associate Gibraltar with Heracles⁷⁷, however, it is known they traveled sometimes with Egyptians to the Red Sea. Fifth, the inherited and insisted upon stories of the Tamil natives of India. Sixth, the discovery of authentic Egyptian hieroglyphs upon the continent of Australia.⁷⁸ Seventh, the description of Solon that Atlantis was an island upon which one could visit the whole known world (therefore, the Orient, India, Australia, Africa, Arabia, Kashmir, Sundaland, and Australia!). Finally, the discovery of sunken land bridges⁷⁹ from Indian myth supporting the tendency of Indian orators to tell the truth, and not pass on bunk stories.

The objections to the myth are the age of the sunken Mauritia⁸⁰, the name of the pillars of Heracles being typically associated with Gibraltar the straits of Bosphorus, and the age of the Tamil bridges (Rama's Bridge or Adam's Bridge) being far more recent, within the same Doggerland like dates, 4-7kya.

Kerguelen Plateau

Another sunken formation, nearly three times the size of Japan, within the Indian Ocean, provides some extra support to the Mauritia-Lemuria theory. One way that the dates for Mauritia may be attacked is due to the gravity anomaly and the generally pick-pocket method of sea core collections. It may simply be a matter of choosing the wrong formations to core, to attain the age of the land. Or, perhaps a gravity anomaly, caused by massive thunderbolts, changed the crystals and made the dating incorrect or unreliable.

However, rather than connect India to Australia, this ridge does appear to be to the southwest of Australia and located on the Antarctic plate. If other crustal displacement theories proved correct, it seems unlikely this formation was above water in the Indian Ocean, but rather in the Atlantic, as part of an Antarctic-Atlantis. It is in the 100+ Mya age range, as well. Although some ancient architect theorists believe in Buddhist myths of humans being millions of years old on this planet, the author contends that so far good biological science restricts us to the chronology as previously outlined.

Dwarka

One of the most promising interpretations of the Lemuria tradition, is that indeed the pillars of Heracles are at the tip of the Gulf of Aden, and that the sunken island was that of Dvaraka (Dwarka). Dwarka was one of the cities of the famed Brahmin empire of Sindhu Kingdom (Yadavas). In the Puranas the city is dedicated to Krishna, and is only one of seven sacred cities.

This city has the advantage of actually being testified in the Mahabharata and associated texts with being sunk in a war in a single day and night, during the war between the Kauravas and Pandavas. It was said that Arjuna visited there.

In the context of EPEMC (see [2]), the Kurukshetra War is the same war of the Aesir and Vanir, or the clash of the titans and gods of Greece, which shook the world, and is a matter of the clash of the heavenly bodies in one system (Jovian) with those of the other system (Saturnian). There was not a lot of literal clashing, however as the SC changed, there were "thunderbirds" and thunderbolts, and at some point Arjuna/Hodr/Adonis/Triton came too close to Earth. By visiting Dvaraka, were they vaporized? Perhaps. It is not known. The date of the Mars' approach and the bringing of Kali's Tongue or the world of Red Dust was

⁷⁵ <https://www.cnn.com/travel/article/lost-continent-mauritius-trnd/index.html>

⁷⁶ <http://discovermagazine.com/2007/nov/did-a-comet-cause-the-great-flood>

⁷⁷ <http://atlantipedia.ie/samples/pillars-of-heracles/>

⁷⁸ <https://sites.google.com/site/electricuniversegateway/recent-news/gosfordglyphsanalysis>

⁷⁹ <http://www.ancient-origins.net/human-origins-opinion-guest-authors/ramas-bridge-where-modern-science-and-ancient-myths-collide>

⁸⁰ At current, ~8.9 million YBP up to 660 million YBP

between 600-700 BCE, which is far too late. So the hero Arjuna does not appear to be the brash Mars/Ares/Thor, but rather a better hero, who is instigated into the “slaying of kin” as Arjuna is (by Krishna). Is this perhaps Hadr? Was Hephaestus banished from Olympus for causing widespread destruction of mankind?

It is not known. However, the Mahabharata offers us a titillating cosmological story as well as real world proof of Atlantis-like destruction in the form of a sunken city.⁸¹

It is not clear why excavations of Dwarka were stopped prematurely. Some conspiracy theories involved American or British archaeology authorities have been supplied by perhaps biased sources,⁸² and yet the idea that the site was completely excavated and nothing more need be learned is laughable at best, and ludicrous as to be a terrible jest, at worst.

In the final analysis, if the stopping of excavation was a conspiracy to hide the discovery of the true Atlantis being an Indian empire of renowned early glory (which is entirely possible), it is successful thus far. There is almost zero discussion as to Dwarka being both Lemuria and Atlantis, despite it being a very real possibility. Is this proof of white-washing of the history, and of anti-POC sentiment in both mainstream archaeology and alternative/diffusionist Atlantology? It is unclear, at the moment. Most Atlantologists are not familiar with the Mahabharata, or Indian myths of Dwarka, even if they are familiar tangentially with Lemuria. It seems that most regard the theory as a side proof that it's possible for Atlantis to exist - just as Doggerland and Sundaland - and that, if anything the *System* is out to suppress the truth about Atlantis, and there is a massive cover-up. After all, the fact that so few Dwarkans know that within a few kilometers the lost fabled city of Dvaraka has been officially found is deplorable, either from an educational point of view or an archaeological and preservation point of view. Such a site, as important as Troy or Giza or Machu Picchu should be lauded and turned into major diving tourism, with continuous excavations. Instead, like Bahamian Row and Santorini, crackdowns against exploration have ensued.

⁸¹ <http://www.bbc.com/earth/story/20160118-the-atlantis-style-myths-of-sunken-lands-that-are-really-true>

⁸² “Dwarka: Atlantis of the East” <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NVLsjx5X3QM>

Photo: Dvaraka, 40m below the sea

Mahabalipuram

This town is still in existence.⁸³ However, in 2004 the Boxing Day tsunami helped pull back the ocean and reveal several sunken or reclaimed (and forgotten) Tamil temples in the east of India. Because the area already is well known and contains over 400 open air temples, it is not a serious contender for Atlantis. However, it is continuous proof that what nature consumes, Mankind forgets.

⁸³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Group_of_Monuments_at_Mahabalipuram

Figure 6 - Lemuria/Kumari Kandam

Mu and/or Zealandia

Of the most mysterious, shocking, and exciting of the continents, the ancient continent of Mu holds some of the greatest promise. What is so perplexing, however, is the discovery of Zealandia simultaneously challenges and yet bolsters Native testimony for Mu.

To review, the following two figures compare the two theoretical continents, one of which has been found by ocean-geologists.:

Figure 7 - Mu, sometimes mistaken for Lemuria (see Figure 6)

Figure 8 - Zealandia with sea level changes

The result of the above analysis is to demonstrate two facts. First, that Mu and Zealandia do not touch in any way. Given that Zealandia is an ancient sunken continent, 23 million YBP,⁸⁴ it makes complete sense that there are no native testimonies for such a continent at all, and in fact Polynesians and aborigines have only ever claimed that the islands of New Zealand and Tasmania remained southeast of Australia. This is not a strike against mu but in the favor of native myth and testimony. As they were right about Sundaland, they were also not wrong about Zealandia.

Secondly, that in fact the Pacific Ocean does contain large, submerged, only recently found land masses, included the world's largest volcano, Tamu Massif (Figure 10).⁸⁵ Also that there can be geological collapses surrounding rifts in PT theory is **very new** to that theory, and yet predicted in EGE (Adams, Meyl), and EPEMC in general (Distinti, Thornhill, Davidson, Careaga).

Figure 9 - Zealandia geology

Figure 10 - Tamir Massif, credit: NatGeo

From this, the author is led to conclude that Zealandia is not Mu. Is there, however, perhaps a continent known as Mu remaining to be discovered?

There are four main pieces of evidence to consider:

1. Hawaiian and Haida ancient testimony regarding ancient arrivals to a vast, wondrous hinterlands.⁸⁶
2. Easter Islander testimony that their volcano is but the last of the remains of a submerged continent that connected them to the Polynesian people⁸⁷, of whom they maintain they are not descended from but are the ancestors of.⁸⁸
3. Teonimanu to the northeast corner of Mu, and Pohnpei to the North, where there appears to be evidence of submerged microcontinents and islands.
4. Worldwide mythic testimony about the rise of continents such as South America,⁸⁹ and sinking of other land masses, which is accompanied by a belief that the Moon passed near to and even crashed into the Earth, perhaps at the Pacific Ocean. (See Figures 11 and 12)

⁸⁴ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Zealandia>

⁸⁵ <https://news.nationalgeographic.com/news/2013/09/130905-tamu-massif-shatsky-rise-largest-volcano-oceanography-science/>

⁸⁶ "Cousins Across the Sea" <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=emg684BXPbQ>

⁸⁷ <https://www.nytimes.com/2017/10/12/science/easter-island-dna-south-america.html>

⁸⁸ See: Redheads of Easter Island

⁸⁹ See "Fingerprints of the Gods", G Hancock, 1995 ; in particular consider the obvious tilt and dumping out of Lake Titicaca.

Figure 11 - Mid-ocean ridges, note the large ridge of the Pacific and Indian oceans

Figure 12 - Ocean crust rift and drift⁹⁰

The sharp uplift of mountain chains such as the Andes and Himalayas, but especially of the Patagonian Torres del Paine,⁹¹ which show clear evidence of massive sudden upthrust,⁹² supports the EPMEC mechanism

⁹⁰ Note the distinct torn part of the southern Pacific rift, where Earth growth is so rapid, that the Pacific plate cannot subduct fast enough on the other side, and so the crust has sheared away near the origin.

⁹¹ http://www.mtsobek.com/assets/images/promotion/78/banner/Patagonia_travel-adventures.jpg

⁹² "When the Earth Nearly Died," D. Allen, 1996

in Table 1. However, the question is, would such uplift across one rift necessitate or be corollary to the sudden sinking on the other side of the rift?

Table 2 - Example evidence of Uplift and Submersion corollaries

Landmass	Uplift Region/value	Downthrust Region/Value
South American Andes	Perú, Bolivia, Titicaca (4 km) ⁹³	
North America	Cascades, Sierras	Guyana, Florida, Appalachia ⁹⁴ (3.2km)
Pacific Coast		Marianas, Philippines
Mid-Atlantic Ridge/Azores		Davis Strait (1.1 km+)
Pacific Ridge		Hawaii, Easter Island
African Rift Valley	Kenya, Tanzania	Anti-Atlas Mountains (2-3 miles)
Western Atlantic		Caribbean, Appalachia
North Atlantic		Greenland, Norway (2.75 km)
Eastern Atlantic		African coast, Canary Isles
Southwestern Pacific	Torres Strait, New Zealand (18 km) ⁹⁵	New South Wales, Indonesia
The Orient	Tibet (3km), Bayan Kara (2 km)	Japan, Indochina (50-300 ft), Sea of Okhotsk, Gobi Desert (600-900m)
Western Europe	British Isles, Alps (~3.7-4 km)	Gibraltar
Eastern Europe	Ural Mountains	Aegean Sea
Indian Subcont+Ocean	Kashmir (6k ft - 1.5 km)	Ganges (2 km of fill)

Please note that the Earth also is surrounded by a 64,000 km (40k miles) *crack* that wraps all around it.⁹⁶

Easter Island

Easter Island is one of the most enigmatic and mysterious locations in the world. For 100 years archaeologists and the media worked together to convince the world that the Moai heads of Easter Island were erected by a vanished people that had destroyed their island's ecosystem and thereby destroyed themselves.⁹⁷ Rather, they were a people that lived in an island dichotomy that was exploited by 17th and 18th century slavers, particularly from Portugal and the Americas, which decimated local populations.⁹⁸

⁹³ Values from "When the Earth Nearly Died", D.S. Allan & J.B. Delair

⁹⁴ aka North Atlantis, *ibid.* P. 33

⁹⁵ "With a horizontal displacement of similar magnitude.", *ibid.* P. 34

⁹⁶ *ibid.* p. 35-36

⁹⁷ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/History_of_Easter_Island

⁹⁸ <http://usslave.blogspot.com/2011/07/slavery-and-disease.html>

Despite this, Easter Islanders (Rap Nui) work today with worldwide archaeological community to unravel the mysteries of the construction methods and reasons of creation of the Moai, as well as of the mysterious Rongorongo script.⁹⁹

One of the mysterious facts about the Moai are that they are actually taller than presupposed.¹⁰⁰ Made completely from volcanic stone in one of two or three quarries, they were then subsequently paraded around the outer edge of the island in a clockwise direction, and left to face outward. Internal strife led to the cessation of the building, presumably as the religious cult's feverish obsession threatened social and family structures and resources, and a rebellion against the tribal leadership ensued. The Rapa Nui subsequently went on with life, venerating the Moai, and fearing their electric eyes, only resuming interest as the rest of the world came to study them as well.

Modern dating dictates that the Moai (spirit statues) were carved 1100-1500 CE, however, the eyes and the strange "topknot" (not likely) upon them demonstrate previously discussed (see "On the Origins of Religions, Appendix B" [2]) astronomical alignments and formations. This would extend their formation to approximately 600-1700 BCE, depending on when the collapse of Mu began, presumably due to the approaches of Venus, and later, Mars. Considering the vector of the "Desert Belt" (see Figure 13), it is entirely likely that such approaches had a rapid uplift (and therefore volcanic explosiveness) followed by sudden collapse. Such a collapse would be preceded by megatsunamis outward (and towards the Deluge myth prone Indian Ocean cultures in Figure 14), and then a reversal of ocean currents, towards the submerging lands, which would precipitate sailing peoples to be set adrift in the Pacific and Indian oceans, as was reported by the sailors of the Gosford Glyphs.

The argument that the Amazon is not a desert will be covered in the section below on Amazonia, but suffice it to say, rains there have long precipitated rapid growth, and ancient destructions would not be easily recognized. Note that the paths proposed (wrapping around, or separate passes) for a lunar, Venetian, or Martian "collision" move across the region of "Mu", Dwarka, and (covered in a later section), Hy'Brasil, and possibly Doggerland and proposed Atlantean locations.¹⁰¹ Note these are not very close pass by pathways but vectors of nearest approach wherein thunderbolts and dust plagues have been reported far out of the norm.

Figure 13 - Desert Belt and proposed "Collision" vectors

⁹⁹ <http://www.ancient-origins.net/unexplained-phenomena/mysterious-rongorongo-writing-easter-island-002242>

¹⁰⁰ <https://www.forbes.com/sites/trevornace/2017/07/26/famous-easter-island-heads-have-hidden-bodies>

¹⁰¹ Note also the coverage of Bolivia, Taklamakan, and Australian deserts, as well as Wyoming, Hudson Bay, and Mexico.

Figure 14 - Flood Myths surrounding Indian Ocean, credit: D. Abbott¹⁰²

One thing that is for sure, at this point, is that mainstream archeology has admitted to massive flooding in multiple places that is geologically recognizable,¹⁰³ and may be the result of a) sudden sea rise, b) ice age meltdown and ancient lake inundations, or c) comet impact and landslide megatsunamis.¹⁰⁴

It is important to remember, however, that **all** of those above mechanisms are explained within the EPEMC mechanisms for catastrophe, as well as a different, Biblically testified phenomena: ocean tidal lift.¹⁰⁵

Teonimanu

This lost, sunken island is part of the Solomon Islands in Melanesia,¹⁰⁶ just northeast of Australia. Although it is not a real contender as "Atlantis", it is possibly from the Atlantean period or at least shares a similar fate, proving (once again) that the issue of sunken land masses is quite possible, and not at all far-fetched.¹⁰⁷ Like many other Solomon Islands, such as Owaraha, the coral reef foundation is partially built upon volcanic soil, and therefore is quite unstable in the face of repeated storms and earthquakes. Similar issues occur within the Bahamas.

¹⁰² <https://malagabay.wordpress.com/2017/03/26/dallas-abbott-the-burckle-impact/>

¹⁰³ <http://egyptday1.blogspot.com/2012/03/egypt-when-egyptian-sahara-became-full.html>

¹⁰⁴ See "Ancient Destructions, Volume 5: Australia Megatsunami 1491 AD", P Mupp

¹⁰⁵ Although the crust would groan, trumpet, and lift (making "Yahweh" sounds while doing so), water as a polar body and a liquid was able to lift for extended periods. We know this is possible because charged electric-vortices known as hurricanes create what is termed "Surge" and can lift water with even a miniscule mass (as compared to a celestial body), upwards of forty feet. As the climate has changed and the SC and GC have begun to alter, hurricanes have increased in size and electrically driven power (out of progression with temperature scales), producing ever more violent and damaging surges. "Hurricane Size Comparison" https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NoxKH_v8b-8

¹⁰⁶ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Teonimanu>

¹⁰⁷ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Category:Former_islands

What is, perhaps more remarkable, is why so many shallow islands had appeared in the first place, only to disappear. If this was a normal process, it would stand to reason that the average new islands and old and sinking islands would be about the same and factor to a near net zero. However, there are definitely more sinking islands than new ones appearing (although they do appear from time to time).¹⁰⁸

Pohnpei

To the north of the Solomon Islands, there lays a more incredible part to the myth of Mu, which forms the “missing link” from Gunung Padang to Easter Island. The island of Pohnpei, which barely remains above the ocean at this point, with most access requiring the use of boat and to traverse thick mangroves and other overgrowth, is the lost city of Nan Madol.¹⁰⁹

This site is so mysterious, it is probably less well known than even the new Nazca lines or the emerging Amazonian earthworks. It is incredibly remote and obscure¹¹⁰. Almost no archaeologists have been, nor have explorers expressed a deep interest in the site. Yet it remains abstruse in the extreme. How so many volcanic plinths, of the same basic hexagonal shape found in Sundaland’s Gunung Padang, could wind up on a sinking reef island in the middle of the mid-Pacific, in typhoon and tsunami territory is quite beyond reason of explanation. The site is not small, either, but incredibly massive, and appears as meticulously planned out (for its resources) as a Angkor Wat.

It is not (it is believed) a remotely antiquarian site, being only a few hundred to a thousand years old. Unless, that is, if it is but one remnant of a sunken continent of Mu.

To be sure, there is no proof that it, Gunung Padang, and Easter Island have anything but Polynesian geology in common. However, consider these facts:

1. There are four sites, including Hawaii, that form the outline of the proposed continent of Mu.
2. There are clear signs of crustal and island collapse in the Pacific Ocean.
3. There are native stories which have, on more than one occasion turned out to be factual testimony.
4. Comet strikes, such as the Melbourne/1491 strike witnessed by Korea and aboriginals of Australia, may have occurred quite commonly, and had widespread devastation.
5. The sinking islands of Mu have all proven to be within human memory, and are a shared belief amongst Polynesians and Micronesians in general, throughout Oceania.

Considering these facts, it would be logical to conclude that a previous golden age may have occurred, and was simply erased by time and circumstance, if not cataclysmic tempest. Teonimanu and Pohnpei, and the western part of Easter Island, and the northern chain

It is with this background that we move forward to consider the Atlantis myth, and some possible candidates which make more sense, and some that have not yet been considered.

¹⁰⁸ <http://www.iflscience.com/environment/rare-glimpse-satellites-catch-birth-two-volcanic-islands/>

¹⁰⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Nan_Madol

¹¹⁰ <https://www.smithsonianmag.com/history/nan-madol-the-city-built-on-coral-reefs-147288758/>

Atlantis/Bahamian Row

Figure 15 - the Fantasy of Atlantis

It is unreasonable to expect that some fantastical elements would pervade the Atlantology community, whether they subscribe to psychics, aliens, etc... is actually irrelevant. After all, Egyptology has clung to ridiculous fantasies for decades.¹¹¹

What is important is if, in following the imagination, more evidence is found that helps shed light. The discovery of Troy was at the whim of a man who refused to believe a fantasy was without reality. His quest was one of fruitlessness and ridicule - until he found it.

In recent history the heroic researches of Alan Wilson and Baram Blackett, and the men they have inspired, have been nothing short of breathtaking. By using the stones and historic bibles, and the language preserved therein (khumry, coelbren, ogden primarily), they were able to follow a trail of breadcrumbs to impeccably preserved historical sites, and unearth the actual headstone of Arturius Rex, King Arthwys (Arthur). They documented the affair, and invited modern, snooty British archaeologists along, who had nothing to do but naysay and gainsay, but they could not prove them wrong with facts.

The point being that these researches were the result of intelligence, courage, imagination, and skill. These are the sort of ingredients you want in science. All men (and women) of celebrated and historical genius

¹¹¹ Giant slave armies and massive ramps to build the Great Pyramid. Khufu. The chiselling of stone with copper. Death cults. Just to name a few.

were just such men: Newton, Galileo, Tesla, Franklin, Archimedes, Socrates, Bohr, Planck, etc... they were all remarkable men of notorious individuality streaks. They did not try to conform to consensus, or to tow the party line. They searched.

Therefore, it is just such a spirit that will be needed to uncover the real Atlantis, because after all, aside from the wide world, the Atlantic has several (half a dozen or more) excellent candidates for Atlantis. The author has placed them in a specific order for discussion, comparing apparent likelihood with evidence, to rank them, as it were. However it is possible that none are favorable, and this will be discussed in the Hidden Atlantis section.

Bermuda Triangle

Perhaps because of the mystery of Bermuda (and the ships it has destroyed due to sinking and hidden reefs), and perhaps because of recent claims of underwater pyramids, this area has become an area of intense focus for the finding of Atlantis. Just as Mu/Oceania has large numbers of sinking volcanic reef islands, the west Atlantic/East Gulf/East Caribbean area does as well.

The discovery of columnar plinths in Bimini (the so called Bimini Road/Row),¹¹² certainly has escalated the feverishness of the search. It is the area that Cayce described. It is a convenient vacation destination, so it is easy to see why casual archaeology (masquerading as very intense archaeology) would be performed by thousands of divers every year in Bimini, fueling the local economy, and the black market treasure hunters.¹¹³

The case for Bimini would be quite high, except for the three most irksome of details:

1. There is no room for a large continent, nor any evidence of one at this location. Lots of sunken islands, and clearly local influence and native stories, but nothing like to a massive continent as seen in Figure 15
2. Both the Canary Islands and Azores remain far more likely for ancient Egyptians to reach in the types of vessels they are known to have produced, than Bimini. Although there are trade currents that move from Africa towards the west, they arrive not in Bimini, but in the south closer to the proposed island of the Piri Reis map.¹¹⁴ See Figure 19.
3. The Bimini Row was probably created more recently, and is since sinking in. The author speculates that the islands were uplifted in volcanic upheavals as recently as 2,000 BC, and are sinking back into the ocean at a very rapid rate. Such unstable land masses seem altogether too unstable for a continent, and yet too stable to sink within a single day.¹¹⁵

¹¹² <http://www.s8int.com/water34.html>

¹¹³ <https://atlantisrisingmagazine.com/article/has-atlantis-finally-been-found-at-bimini/>

¹¹⁴ In the days of the Triangle Trade, after using the winds to go west and north, traders would then ride the gulf current back northeast towards Europe. See: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Triangular_trade

¹¹⁵ Arguments have been made for comets and megatsunamis, which indeed may have sunk islands in Mu as well, however, the description according to Solon was that the crust itself seemed to split open and the sea swallowed Atlantis, and not merely that it was over flooded and washed off the top of an atoll, only to later sink. At any rate, columns found in Bimini may only be there as a result of swift tsunamis, and could have originated anywhere in the east Caribbean. Remember it is postulated in this paper that the sinking was caused by sudden crustal deformation, due to the passing by of the Moon upon its capture. Looking into the Enuma Elish, "In the myth recorded on cuneiform tablets, the deity Enki (later Ea) believed correctly that Apsu was planning to murder the younger deities, upset with the chaos they created, and so captured him and held him prisoner beneath his temple the E-Abzu. This angered Kingu, their son, who reported the event to Tiamat, whereupon she fashioned eleven monsters to battle the deities in order to avenge Apsu's death. These were her own offspring: Bašmu ("Venomous Snake"), Ušumgallu ("Great Dragon"), Mušmahhū ("Exalted Serpent"), Mušhuššu ("Furious Snake"), Laḥmu (the "Hairy One"), Ugallu (the "Big Weather-Beast"), Uridimmu ("Mad Lion"), Girtablullū ("Scorpion-Man"), Umū dabrūtu ("Violent Storms"), Kulullū ("Fish-Man") and Kusarikku ("Bull-Man"). Tiamat possessed the Tablet of Destinies and in the primordial battle she gave them to Kingu, the deity she had chosen as her lover and the leader of her host, and who was also one of her children. The deities gathered in terror, but Anu, (replaced later, first by Enlil and, in the late version that has survived after the First Dynasty of Babylon, by Marduk, the

The other aspect to consider is that the claimed columns appear, frankly speaking, to be typical columnar basalt, with nothing unique or impressionable about them. People argue that the age of Atlantis is the reason for the wear, however the preservation of Dvaraka, and Heracleion cast much doubt on this theory. Indeed the plinths are much too small as compared to other Atlantean, Tepe, Archaic or Megalithic Period megaliths, such as those at Tiahuanaco, Baalbek, Karnak, or Ollantaytambo (See Appendix for Megalith weight and size comparisons).

In summary the Bimini location provides a conveniently placed distraction, so close to North America it must be presumed that North America itself is actually Atlantis, rendering it rather unlikely as it is also altogether too far away from Gibraltar. There is also scant proof that the Bermuda Triangle is anymore destructive of ships and airplanes than other areas of reef-filled seas around the world. Therefore the sense that "Something weird is happening, it must be where Atlantis sunk," is far too unscientific to deem a tenable theory. However, the author admits that anything is possible.

Canary Islands

One of the most obvious theories for Atlantis is exactly what one expects: land just passed the pillars of Gibraltar. The islands are, conveniently, highly volcanically active, and even the point of [speculative] origins of future megatsunami destruction.¹¹⁶ This, logically, does not present any real evidence, only the growing sense about the islands that the region is unstable enough that perhaps destruction could have befallen the region.

Secondly, the islands are home to mysterious sets of step pyramids which were, at first, attributed to very modern dates or even forgeries (knockoffs). Later they were confirmed to be of mythic origins by the local population. However, there is nothing about them to suggest Atlantean age. It is also unlikely and unlogical to suppose that such well built step pyramids would survive such a disastrous catastrophe virtually unscathed.

The thing that the Canary Islands have going for them, aside from (again) convenient proximity, is the same effect as explained in Easter Island myth, and with the Sri Lankan Tamils: that *most* of the island sank, but not the highest points, which would presumably have been much, much taller.

Geologically, the Canary Islands are much like the Hawaiian islands. They rise from volcanic hotspot activity, and then sink later on as the plate moves along.¹¹⁷ In theory this would provide a very logical explanation for a potentially large island sinking catastrophe.¹¹⁸ However, the islands themselves, like Bimini, constitute a much too small area, of all too great a convenience, which itself speaks to a separate theory: that the islands were outposts for the Atlantean empire, and have suffered general decay of the culture, but retained enough to pay homage to "the gods" by the building of pyramids, called maroiços.

There is simply not enough room for a realistic Atlantis of fantastical legend to have been in the Canary Islands. Although some persons make out the realism to be improved by scaling down the size of the city and

son of Ea), first extracting a promise that he would be revered as "king of the gods", overcame her, armed with the arrows of the winds, a net, a club, and an invincible spear.

“And the lord stood upon Tiamat’s hinder parts,
And with his merciless club he smashed her skull.
He cut through the channels of her blood,
And he made the North wind bear it away into secret places.”

Slicing Tiamat in half, he made from her ribs the vault of heaven and earth. Her weeping eyes became the source of the Tigris and the Euphrates, her tail became the Milky Way. With the approval of the elder deities, he took from Kingu the Tablet of Destinies, installing himself as the head of the Babylonian pantheon. Kingu was captured and later was slain: his red blood mixed with the red clay of the Earth would make the body of humankind, created to act as the servant of the younger Igigi deities. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tiamat>

¹¹⁶ <https://www.express.co.uk/news/world/865079/La-Palma-volcano-eruption-mega-tsunami-warning-Spain-Europe-alert-Cumbre-Vieja-tenerife>

¹¹⁷ <http://www.mantleplumes.org/Canary.html>

¹¹⁸ If the whole of Mauna Loa sank into the Pacific overnight, it would constitute the loss of about 2.46% of the size of California, or about the size of San Diego county, less the city of San Diego itself.

its island (thinking, perhaps, that to neolithic peoples even a dungheap would be impressive) it probably diminishes the likelihood of a) the existence of an empire, b) its access to the whole of the world, and c) the calling of it, “a continent.”

While it is beyond the scope of the paper to analyze the etymology of the word, it is assuredly a great error for Plato or Solon, much less anyone else to translate a small island as a “continent.” Therefore, the author maintains we must seek entire sunken *landmasses*, and not mere islands or atolls, or even cities.

Azores

However, the trail is hot. In the search for Atlantis through the *historical* “Pillars of Heracles”, that is the Strait of Gibraltar, there is a large landmass of sufficient area, with great access (both in distance, and time), which sits upon the requisite geology to conform to our HEGEME¹¹⁹ model of crustal deformation and collapse: the Azores (see Figure 15).

Figure 16 - The Mid-Atlantic Ridge; centered: the Azorean plateau¹²⁰

¹¹⁹ Hollow-Expanding-Growing-Electro-Magnetic-Earth

¹²⁰ Which lies within striking distance immediately passed Gibraltar, and conveniently located for the trade of “the entire world”: Britain, Spain, Africa, North America, Iceland, etc..

Figure 17 - Hotspots of the World

At present the islands of Azores are all that remain of the plateau,¹²¹ which was, geologically speaking, destroyed by a massive caldera explosion.¹²² More enticingly is that some sea core samples suggest this was possibly between 20kya and 100kya, making it the most probable candidate. In a criminal lineup, this suspect most fits the description.¹²³

And it's extremely inconvenient. The depth of the plateau at present is between 200 and 2000 meters deep. Just deep enough to present a problem (other than massive area). At that depth, shallow scuba diving is very dangerous and basically untenable. Yet, there are hardly any lab-based submarines that are dedicated for a search for Atlantis. This means, for the most part, the search will continue with bathymetry and underwater 3D radar, which is great, but produces wild inaccuracies.¹²⁴

However, the author contends this is the region of water which, for a main Atlantis **proper** should be most considered and most thoroughly searched, and researched, as it is likely that the waves crashing into the island would indeed produce vast destructive consequences including burying the island, potentially beneath an already thick layer of pyroclastic flow from a supervolcanic explosion.¹²⁵

Note, such things cannot solely be done via Google Earth, although the Internet has tried. The author admits, such methods hold promise, although often do nothing but waste our attentions.¹²⁶

¹²¹ <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/62459376.pdf>

¹²² https://notendur.hi.is/~ers12/skrar/Azores%20TJ%20and%20HS_presentation_Einar%20Ragnar.pdf

¹²³ https://en.wikiversity.org/wiki/Atlantis/Location_Hypotheses#cite_note-177

¹²⁴ <http://arl.nus.edu.sg/twiki6/pub/ARL/BibEntries/Potter1999b.pdf>

¹²⁵

https://en.wikiversity.org/wiki/Atlantis/Location_Hypotheses#A_LARGE_GEOLOGICALLY_ANCIENT_CALDERA_EXISTS_BELOW_THE_AZORES_PLATEAU_AND_ERUPTED

¹²⁶ <https://ancient-code.com/lost-city-atlantis-spotted-google-earth/> 31 24 25. 58" N 24 32 09. 08" W (4500 meters)

Figure 18 - Azorean Plateau "continent" (close in) credit: Yang et al

Piri Reis Map

Now, however, although the Azores began to represent the best scientifically based evidence, historical anthropology has produced a rather interesting hiccup in the hypothesis. Although it had been known about for many centuries and studied, the notoriety of the Piri Reis Map (see Figure 19 pg 37) has been discussed.¹²⁷

It isn't that the map is about Atlantis, but that it has a) remarkably accurate depictions of the South American and Antarctic coasts,¹²⁸ b) including Antarctic rivers, and c) so blazingly highlights the large island and no other in the Atlantic that is larger, but instead a couple smaller ones (perhaps Trinidad and Tobago or Puerto Rico, see Figure 20).

However, there are three things that the author wants to make explicitly understood about this map, and cartography of that period.

1. There were no book stores, encyclopedia Britannica, or other more reliable sources to use. Before the invention of the chronometer, longitude measurement was extremely difficult. Most of the precision in mapping came from actual surveying of the coasts, which could take a long time.
2. This map is clearly more accurate below the Tropic of Cancer (roughly Nicaragua). Florida is not nearly as precise as Brazil. This suggests the sources of the mapping were quite possibly Portuguese, and were the result of empire-sanctioned surveying.
3. The landmass that looks like it might be Atlantis is therefore most probably the Dominican Republic, or Cuba, or a vague combination of the two, which were combined somehow by Arabic sailors.

¹²⁷ <http://www.lost-civilizations.net/possible-physical-evidence-atlantis.html>

¹²⁸ Antarctica was not officially discovered until 1775; clearly, as this map was at least as old as 1513, and its creator maintained its sources were of older, ie *ancient* sources, this is incorrect history.

Figure 20 - Piri Reis Comparison of subject area.

It may never be known the sources of Piri Reis' map. Sailors of that period often took their maps and secrets to the grave, or to Davy Jones' locker (at the bottom of the sea). However, the map remains a confusing red herring in the search for a real Atlantis, and adds fuel to the fire for the Bimini Row theorists, despite being clearly south of the Bermuda Triangle.

Geologically speaking, the area is mountainous and volcanic, as well as full of yearly destructive hurricanes. It would be, logically speaking, a very possible region. Aside from a deep gashing underwater canyon surrounded by volcanoes, the nearby Yucatan and Nicaraguan coasts,¹²⁹ would have been quite extended in the Younger Dryas period (see Figure 21), and quite populated by Olmec or Pre-Olmec powers and would explain a lot.

Figure 21 - Mid-Cayman Underwater Canyon

¹²⁹ <http://shadow.eas.gatech.edu/~jean/Came2007.pdf>

For example, no one has ever understood how the Olmec stone heads had both negroid and Asiatic features.¹³⁰ Nor how they created the “Mayan” calendar despite being in the jungles. Nor how that calendar’s similar roots have been found across the Atlantic.¹³¹

Could the Olmec be, after all, like the Basque, Phoenicians, or Algonquians, proposed descendants of the lost Atlantean culture? Could their destruction have been misheard or mis-reported by frightened Egyptians fleeing the eruptions of violent volcanoes? Reporting that the entire continent was destroyed, rather than the mere coast? Or perhaps an entire island as is shown in the Piri Reis map was destroyed, as was the pre-Olmec tradition, and these were the origins of both the Viracocha and Quetzalcoatl traditions, as well as the source of the “redheads” of Easter Island, who mistakenly remembered the oral traditions backwards (westward as “Mu”, instead of Eastwards).

The problems with these speculations are many, as they are firstly endless. They lose a central thread, as it were, much as a person gets lost in the self-same Mayan jungles. Although the Maya have taught us to be cautious in ruling anything out, it must be pointed out that much of the land remained above the sea, and the coast would have retreated, yes, but not in a day and a night, however fast the YD melt occurred. Although Sundaland was swallowed up, it was not swallowed up in a day and a night, nor was Doggerland or Mu.

The trail begins to unravel again, and in the sections that follow, more questions are raised than answers, bringing us to three startling conclusions in the last section.

Spain

When studying the modern sea levels, it is easy to see why Atlantologists, even well trained ones, may make very strange decisions. The thinking behind the Spanish “Dona Ana Park” site¹³² is as follows:

1. During the Younger Dryas, the Pillars of Heracles may have actually been closed up (see Figure 22).
2. The story may have been passed along incorrectly, in that perhaps it was a civilization *close to* the famous pillars, where they were the home.
3. Therefore, look for *footprints* of the famed Atlantean architecture,¹³³ which may reveal, at last a realistic Atlantis.¹³⁴
4. Iberian peninsula is very central to the “Old World”, considering all the access it provides (compare to Spanish Empire).
5. The Basque people and their mysterious language and genetics may provide the most physical proof of Atlantis (aside from a city) that we can get.¹³⁵
6. Wouldn’t it be great if they found such a city in a marsh?^{136 137 138}

Realistically, however, this hypothesis has problems. One of the facts that it rests upon (as scientific as it is), basically excludes the marsh from being an Ice Age recipient of a tsunami, because the coastline will

¹³⁰

<https://www.pvamu.edu/tiphc/research-projects/afro-mexicans-afromestizos/exploration-of-african-presence-in-meso-america-the-olmecs/>

¹³¹ <https://peopleofonefire.com/we-will-have-to-rethink-the-early-history-of-the-mayas-and-indeed-north-america.html>

¹³² <https://www.ibtimes.co.uk/more-signs-mythical-city-atlantis-its-mysterious-civilisation-found-spanish-marsh-1603470>

¹³³ “[117d] And after crossing the three outer harbors, [117e] one found a wall which began at the sea and ran round in a circle, at a uniform distance of fifty stades from the largest circle and harbor, and its ends converged at the seaward mouth of the channel. The whole of this wall had numerous houses built on to it, set close together; while the sea-way and the largest harbor were filled with ships and merchants coming from all quarters, which by reason of their multitude caused clamor and tumult of every description and an unceasing din night and day.” ~ Plato, transl. R.G. Bury

¹³⁴ See this, and other location attempts using this hypothesis: http://www.atlantismaps.com/chapter_7.html

¹³⁵ <https://atlantisrisingmagazine.com/article/the-basqueatlantis-connection/>

¹³⁶ <https://news.nationalgeographic.com/2015/03/150318-atlantis-morocco-santorini-plato-adams-ngbooktalk/>

¹³⁷ http://www.nbcnews.com/id/42072469/ns/technology_and_science-science/t/lost-city-atlantis-believed-found-spain/#.WuUdjy7wYdU

¹³⁸ Speaking as a *Careaga*, a Basque descendent, of course it would. But that is not necessarily realistic.

have been significantly different at that time, than from when the marsh was hit by a modern tsunami. The scientists, as is typical, try to reform the time period of Critias to conform with Egyptology, and move the dates of Atlantis into the distant, *but not too distant* past.

Figure 22 - Bathymetry of Mediterranean in Younger Dryas (surface above sea level in orange)

Figure 23 - Dona Ana Park Marsh reconstruction credit: NatGeo

This shows how little the archeology community, even as concerns Atlantis and the big money of James Cameron, has in the way of concern about the lessons of Gobekli Tepe. That is to say: none at all. As far as the mainstream is concerned, any real Atlantis must conform to a post Giza world, or near to Giza enough. Which means nothing in the extreme. However, the author must remind the reader that Plato had very specific writings concerning the events.

“Many great deluges have taken place during the nine thousand years, for that is the number of years which have elapsed since the time of which I am speaking; and during all this time and through so many changes, there has never been any considerable accumulation of the soil coming down from the mountains, as in other places, but the earth has fallen away all round and sunk out of sight. The consequence is, that in comparison of what then was, there are remaining only the bones of the wasted body, as they may be called, as in the case of small islands, all the richer and softer parts of the soil having fallen away, and the mere skeleton of the land being left. But in the primitive state of the country, its mountains were high hills covered with soil, and the plains, as they are termed by us, of Phelleus were full of rich earth, and there was abundance of wood in the mountains. Of this last the traces still remain, for although some of the mountains now only afford sustenance to bees, not so very long ago there were still to be seen roofs of timber cut from trees growing there, which were of a size sufficient to cover the largest houses; and there were many other high trees, cultivated by man and bearing abundance of food for cattle. Moreover, the land reaped the benefit of the annual rainfall, not as now losing the water which flows off the bare earth into the sea, but, having an abundant supply in all places, and receiving it into herself and treasuring it up in the close clay soil, it let off into the hollows the streams which it absorbed from the heights, providing everywhere abundant fountains and rivers, of which there may still be observed sacred memorials in places where fountains once existed; and this proves the truth of what I am saying.” ~Critias, Plato¹³⁹

In this context, and with regard to being *past* the Pillars of Heracles, and of being a lost, sunken continent, and not merely Iberia, the hypothesis has fallen completely flat on its face, except in one regard. It has been theorized that, after all, Atlantis was not only a place but a people, and an expansive empire, which may have shipped its ideas elsewhere, or rebuilt them again after a destruction, in which case, the Dona Ana Park site may be regarded as a possible satellite location, or a trace of Atlantis. Yet, almost certainly, nothing more.¹⁴⁰

Hy’Brasil

One of the more interesting, and most obscure Atlantean legends, which remains completely within possibility of existence, is Hy’Brasil, or Brasil for short. The island is a mythic Celtic wonderland,¹⁴¹ which existed north to Ireland and south of Iceland (and therefore quite a bit balmy, given the gulf stream which flows thence). There is, as of yet, little proof of such an island. However, the discovery of Doggerland which has cooled the search for Brasil, will also likely fuel its search. The fact that it has appeared so often on middle age maps begs the question of how the myth appeared.¹⁴²

¹³⁹ <http://classics.mit.edu/Plato/critias.html>

¹⁴⁰ As convenient as that would be for an anti-diffusionist mainstream that would love for the box to be so closed as to keep Atlantis *just inside* the Mediterranean, where it can keep an eye on it.

¹⁴¹ [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Brasil_\(mythical_island\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Brasil_(mythical_island))

¹⁴² <http://www.ancient-origins.net/unexplained-phenomena/hy-brasil-legendary-phantom-island-ireland-003608>

Figure 24 - Hy'Brasil

The author makes no claims of knowledge. It is not known if an island of celtic gods once existed. However, it does indeed sound like a fantasy of folklore, which has little to no basis in historical fact. There are some shoals, but they are inconsequential. The map could have been merely a place added. In China entire "bestiaries" were created (not unlike today¹⁴³) which, inherited by bored feudal nobles, were taken to be real, and then added upon by charlatan "scientists" working for the imperial court. John Dee did something similar in the field of alchemy. Therefore, it is entirely possible that the island was added to please a Gaelic lord, and that it was merely copied, several times, as a matter of "standard." Vanishing islands cannot be ruled out, nor can they be proven.¹⁴⁴

It is, at any rate, not a continent.

Antarctica

Antarctica, however, is. Moreover, it is clear from the Piri Reis map (although ice core samples disagree), that perhaps not all of it was ice, and some may have even been inhabitable. Setting aside spurious claims of mega pyramids, there was one (widely and infamously) promulgated theory of crustal displacement,¹⁴⁵ which has been since discredited, and which had allowed that Antarctica could have been north of its present location by as much as 2,000 miles or so. Such a theory relies, also on thin crustal branes, which can (and do) suddenly move with violent ferocity. However, although HEGEME supports this aspect of Hapgood's idea, the Atlantis connection is (for the moment), entirely erroneous.

The following is an inexhaustive list of problems:

1. Such a movement would create an ultra-mega tsunami which would have left errata signs upon itself and all over the world.

¹⁴³ One must wonder if stories like "Fantastic Beasts and Where to Find Them" by JK Rowling might not become a citation in several centuries as proof of our cultures' superstitious mindset.

¹⁴⁴ Perhaps it disappeared in the Bermuda Triangle.

¹⁴⁵ <http://www.thetruthhunter.com/earth-crust-displacement-atlantis/>

2. Global Diluvian errata and Ice Age errata can, and do, exist outside the normal locations, however, not in the widespread volume (but far more sparsely, requiring another flood or ice age to move them around) needed.
3. The fauna upon and beneath the continent appear well adapted for the climate. They seem neither strong enough to survive such a cataclysm (for surely it would be accompanied by massive caldera eruptions).
4. There are no “Scrape Marks” on the Atlantic seabed
5. Nor are there mega sized ash layers in that time period, in Antarctic ice cores.
6. The myth relates a sinking of an island, not its relocation or motivation.
7. The continent of Atlantis and Antarctica do share high mountains, but as far as we know, not recent forestation.
8. Antarctica has many thousands feet thick of ice, which requires far too much time to be since Atlantis.
9. Ice core samples and dating are a very reliable science, more so than carbon dating.
10. They are verified using Greenland samples.
11. In HEGEME, such a displacement is always followed by massive crustal buckling and pileup, such as the Himalayas, or Andes.
12. Nor is it as fast and extreme as a single day and a night.
13. The mid ocean ridges do not support such a change, nor is there a missing “hole” in the southern part of the MAR which would be explained by a “scab” of continental crust slipping away to the South.

A far simpler explanation of the Piri Reis map is that it is using variable scale cartography. The top and the bottom of the map are scaled downward, as compared to the Equatorial portion of the map, to save room. Therefore the antarctica pictured is simply “moved up”, and does not reflect *actual distance*. Its presence at all suggests it is a warning of a dangerous cape, which sailors must avoid at all costs.

Santorini & Heracleion

Before heading into the deeply obscure, it might be prudent to give these two locations a chance to be the Atlantis the mainstream wants them to be. It seems, inside the Mediterranean, that Atlantis multiples year by year. If Alexandria wasn't already known to be Alexandria, it would undoubtedly be also Atlantis.

This is the strange case of Heracleion, which, upon finding, gave its finder the credit of “having found Atlantis.”¹⁴⁶ It is unclear how to take such headlines, as they are somewhere between sensationalism and bold-faced-lying. They are unscientific claims, to say the least, because Thonis-Heracleion is a legendary city in its own right.¹⁴⁷

However, with Santorini there is something very compelling about the exploded island, and its Akrotiri culture which was wiped out, that touches us in the search for Atlantis. Perhaps it is the horror of Pompeii, and its frozen-as-statue citizenry, which makes us think with shuddering fright at the power of being *on the island* with the volcano as the “end” came. Did the culture get mostly blasted away at one? Or did some of it slide into the sea as a landslide? Were they able to flee? If so, when did this happen, and why? How did the local sea cultures react? Certainly legends and sorrowful tales must have spread out from the epicenter. One can only speculate, and look to the results of good archaeology, and the culture they have unearth, at either site.

¹⁴⁶ <https://www.telegraph.co.uk/art/what-to-see/sunken-cities-the-man-who-found-atlantis/>

¹⁴⁷ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Heracleion>

However, one can also set aside these two claims, as they fail to meet most of the requirements. For example, the Santorini blast was witnessed and remembered afterwards in the mythic libraries of the middle east and Egypt, and even as far as China (where climate was impacted).¹⁴⁸

This is hardly saying that the event was so remote that *only one source* remembered it (The Egyptian Priest, who told Solon). After all, the Minoans there, and maybe in Crete, were devastated. **Everyone** knew about it. This is not something that can be said for Atlantis (although it could for Dwarka).

As for Thonis-Heracleion, like so many sunken and lost cities, all along the coasts worldwide, sometimes they simply fell into ruin, disrepair, and abandonment. As the city began to slip into the sea, it seems most likely that the people merely left, and as the city was of no more use or importance, it too was “forgotten.” But it was not literally forgotten. And at any rate, it sank around the same time as Plato, again, well within Hellene memory.

The Black Sea

As the curiosity thickens again, the truly obscure ideas begin to emerge about *alternative* Atlantean theories. That is to say, uncommon and highly irregular ones. If one studies, for instance, Figure 22 with great “unboxed” eyes, one will notice that the Mediterranean was divided, as if by half. Furthermore that the Black Sea perhaps did not exist at that time. This presents two or three golden opportunities for “lost civilizations.” For one, the entire Aegean region and upper Italy becomes, as it were, a continent of its own. It seems unlikely to be the explanation, however, it is not without merit or possibility.

Secondly, any mountainous peoples dwelling (unwisely) beneath the current sea level, unaware of the break in the razor thin isthmus dam at Gibraltar was impending, would be completely washed away. This is not supposition, it is almost certainly fact. People would have followed the retreating coasts *downward*, in order to keep alive as the Younger Dryas progressed, and they would have been like fish in a barrel when the waters came storming back in.

Thirdly, at what is now Istanbul and the Straits of Bosphorus there could have been radically tall cliffs that would qualify (and to their credit be closer to Greece, and more dearly known) as “Pillars of Heracles”, who could have been, actually, a Sumero-Babylonian legend brought to Greece (via Gilgamesh myth). The breakage of that thin isthmus dam would have proceeded from the refilling of the Mediterranean in the Tepe Period,¹⁴⁹ explaining, also, the appearance of those people (as if suddenly removed from elsewhere). Couple this with Crimean/Cimmerian legends,¹⁵⁰ which may have been related to Black Sea mega-flooding and one has the makings of massive human diffusionist movement.

Putting it all together, one begins to get the sense that - around the world - a vast antediluvian culture which had sprung up was, in the whole, wiped out by a) cataclysmic impact, b) volcanos, c) super-tsunamis, d) rising sea levels (fast), e) mega-floods as the Ocean moved to fill in missing regions previously lost, f) cosmic induced crustal displacements,¹⁵¹ and g) ensuing famine, drought, and disease.

In fact, other than the Azores and possible circular cities, the entire Atlantean myth appears to be, like the Noah’s Flood myth, a **worldwide human tale of survival**. It appears, rather, to be a description of humanity’s civilized condition in the Golden Age, which was like an “empire”... an empire of consciousness. The diffusion was, undoubtedly, trade wind related, and this probably explains the Olmec “old world” contact observations, as well as the touch of Eurasian which Native American languages sometimes possess.

The question is, does it constitute the existence of a lost continent of Atlantis myth?

¹⁴⁸ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Minoan_eruption

¹⁴⁹ <https://www.beyondsciencetv.com/2017/11/30/5-clues-that-a-global-flood-actually-happened/>

¹⁵⁰ “Between the time when the oceans drank Atlantis, and the rise of the sons of Aryas, there was an age undreamed of.” ~Conan the Barbarian

¹⁵¹ It cannot be overstated or underscored enough here to remind the audience that even *slight* changes in orbits in the Jovian or Saturnian eras would have resulted in drastic shifts on Earth, due to the overwhelming power of electromagnetism.

Hidden Atlantis hypothesis

Perhaps this is a very strange concept, posited by the author, considering the fact that Atlantis is already hidden. On the whole, the concept does refer to the loss of culture, consciousness, and the civilization balance that once existed (reputedly) in a bygone era of human history, that has obviously been replaced with religious[2] and apocalyptic obsessions[5].

The “Hidden” Atlantis concept is not a mothership, or El Dorado. Rather it is the idea that the truth has become literally buried in a quagmire of geophysical and historical alterations, such that the very concept of Atlantis, not to mention its physical location, have themselves become obscured.

It follows upon the psychological concept of “repressed memories”.

Remember earlier, when it was mentioned that the Semites likely arrived in Egypt not as slaves, initially, but as refugees? That they took to one leader, Akhenaten, or perhaps a real Moses¹⁵², and they made the events in Exodus into a closely **personal tale**, is not unreasonable as a supposition. Suppose, for an instant that this people had been, like the Dogon and many others, heavily displaced. Even by thousands of miles. It is, therefore, not unreasonable to suppose that their myths would have altered over time.

Similarly, if the people that became the First Dynasty Egyptians (like their successors) were not *of* Egypt but were migrant to and inheritors of her, then they, too, may have repressed memories, and indeed, strange tales to tell.

Open the mind for a bit, for the author to draw attention to the single largest source of a “continent” destroying myth that has yet to raise awareness.

Figure 25 - The Sahara Savannah, a “sea” of grass and lakes, desertified

To be sure the Sahara desert does not constitute an island, in an ocean. Instead, a “Buried” Atlantis would be suggested that, aside from an island *somewhere*, if an island ever existed which fits the bill, there was, almost ironclad 100% positive entire civilizations of Atlantean Period peoples that were swallowed up in

¹⁵² That Moses is not mentioned directly in Egyptian glyphs possibly speaks to the borrowing of the character of their favorite pharaoh and culturally appropriating him for their own literary devices. The same argument has been made for Christ about Buddha, or Buddha about Krishna, or Krishna about Horus.

the sands of time and desert. In literal terms, they were buried in the sea of sand by either lunar or Venetian sands (or possibly another body in the Saturnian system).

There are three ways we can prove this.

1. It is not possible for several feet of topsoil to produce hundreds of feet of depth of sand, in the Sahara, in under 12,000 years.¹⁵³
2. The region itself would have been home to millions, potentially hundreds of millions of people.
3. The area is large enough to constitute a continent, and it does appear to be the home of mystery, fear, and awe the world over.

Although people can, and do live in the Sahara, they strive to stay away from the center, naturally, and almost all the migration has been away from the core to the fringes. Egypt and Jordan, Morocco and Algeria, South Sudan, Kenya, and Ethiopia have been the places of mass congregation both of people, and of cultural memory. Though terrifying sometimes, the Nile (which cut through the sands, easily) constitutes a great protective barrier from whatever terror befell the north of Africa in the Younger Dryas.

Certain geological wonders are strewn throughout the mysterious and vast ocean-sized desert, some of which have proved invaluable to astronomy in the proving of lost planet collisions.¹⁵⁴

While this theory is not of Atlantis, it is of Atlantean cultures. The evidence for the purported “empire” seems to include areas as far away as Crimea, Armenia, and Egypt, with touches in Mexico, Bolivia, and Mauritius, Dwarka, and maybe north into the Balkans and Russia. How, therefore can such a civilization exist without ports, land, and other cultural signs? Perhaps, in fact, it did, and its remnants became Egypt, Sumer, the Basque and Olmec. However, by the time those civilizations emerged, the chaos of 5000+ years of fear of the wrath of the god(s) and pushed the memory of the culture almost completely away. Only the most sensation bits, such as the sinking of (perhaps) the Azores, and of the great civilizing culture which once spread everywhere, was repressed and forgotten. Except by those whose professional job it was, to memorize such things.

This theory, as of yet, is without merit, and should not be considered a real Atlantis theory. Yet it should not be dismissed, because the imagination that it demands may yield massive results in the search through sands and rocks of time.

Amazonia

Although there is not room for a lengthy exercise in analysis of the lost civilization of the Amazon, it is worth pointing out that it also conforms to *some* of the aspects of the story. How? Essentially, the Amazon River basin is, for the most part, near to sea level. Supposing, for a moment, that the seas were at their present, or near present levels, if there were a very massive Deluge or Great Flood,¹⁵⁵ such as proposed in the Enuma Elish, then it would stand to reason that the inundating waters of such a tsunami could be what wiped out the mysterious earthworks civilization of Amazonia.

There is, at present, no valuable data regarding the end, except for the myths reported from South America about the Great Flood, and the earthworks, which are in “On the Origins of Religions” [1].

“Moving to South America, we encounter the Chibcas of central Colombia. According to their myths, they had originally lived as savages, without laws, agriculture or religion. Then one day there appeared

¹⁵³ <http://piecubed.co.uk/sand-facts/>

¹⁵⁴

<https://www.independent.co.uk/news/science/diamonds-meteorite-lost-planet-hidden-solar-system-birth-earth-epfl-a8308861.html>

¹⁵⁵ There was actually both a Great Flood and then separately a Deluge (storm). <http://nwcreation.net/noahlegends.html>

among them an old man of a different race. He wore a thick long beard and his name was Bochica. He taught the Chibcas how to build huts and live together in society.

His wife, who was very beautiful and named Chia, appeared after him, but she was wicked and enjoyed thwarting her husband's altruistic efforts. Since she could not overcome his power directly, she used magical means to cause a great flood in which the majority of the population died. Bochica was very angry and exiled Chia from the earth to the sky, where she became the moon given the task of lighting the nights. He also caused the waters of the flood to dissipate and brought down the few survivors from the mountains where they had taken refuge.

Thereafter he gave them laws, taught them to cultivate the land and instituted the worship of the sun with periodic festivals, sacrifices and Pilgrimages.

When they were discovered, the Tupinamba Indians of Brazil venerated a series of civilizing or creator heroes. The first of these heroes was Monan (ancient, old) who was said to have been the creator of mankind but who then destroyed the world with flood and fire ...

The Araucnians of pre-Colombian Chile preserved a tradition that there was once a flood which very few Indians escaped. The survivors took refuge on a high mountain called Thegtheg (the thundering or the glittering) which had three peaks and the ability to float on water.

In the far south of the continent a Yamana legend from Tierra del Fuego states: The moon woman caused the flood. This was at the time of the great upheaval ... Moon was filled with hatred towards human beings ...

At that time everybody drowned with the exception of those few who were able to escape to the five mountain peaks that the water did not cover.

Another Tierra del Fuegan tribe, the Pehuenche, associate the flood with a prolonged period of darkness: The sun and the moon fell from the sky and the world stayed that way, without light, until finally two giant condors carried both the sun and the moon back up to the sky." - Hancock, Fingerprints of the Gods, p. 188

The very fact that so many different tribes of South America have massive flood myths concerning the moon (matching the Tiamat myth of Sumer), is telling. Indeed it seems reasonable to imagine an entire **shelf** of water arising and moving inland, destroying nearly completely the evidence of an advanced civilization in the Amazon.

However, the evidence, if any remains, of such a flood would be *hidden and buried*, beneath the canopy of trees.

Figure 26 - Amazonia, the flooded world of Ancient Amazon?

Notable Mentions

Before concluding the paper, it might be noteworthy to mention, briefly, some of the most notable Atlantisesque cities and stories that have recently emerged, to underscore the value of this field to history and archaeology:

Yonaguni

This Japanese city is quite controversial,¹⁵⁶ although very famous now, due to the frequent citations by Graham Hancock and John Anthony West (deceased). It is based upon the scientific research of only one major archaeologist, Masaaki Kimura, Professor Emeritus of the University of Ryukyus (like Gunung Padang and Bosnia and originally, Gobekli Tepe). The reports coming from his agency and group of dedicated followers are that the age is right around 10-12 kya, which would match descriptions of sea level rise.¹⁵⁷

However, some dissenting opinions, as usual, claim the formations seen in the highly videographed and photographed location are natural. Some of them seem likely to be natural, while others are undoubtedly not, and Dr. Kimura's analysis is likely to be held up under close scrutiny. However, he did buckle under pressure and change the dating to be in the 2-3 kya range, to match sea levels, and undoubtedly make the mainstream community feel better about the situation. His main detractor is, after all, an archeologist (and not a geologist).

¹⁵⁸

¹⁵⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Yonaguni_Monument

¹⁵⁷ <http://www.ancient-origins.net/ancient-places-oceania/mysterious-10000-year-old-underwater-ruins-japan-00817>

¹⁵⁸ Richard J. Pearson

Lake Van Fort

Although this is a lake, and it is a fort, and this is in no way, shape, or form the lost city of Atlantis, the find did take the archeological community by surprise because it happened amidst so many other announcements.¹⁵⁹

The fort was located on the shore of a very large and militarily important lake in Turkey. It, over time sank while the lake depth rose. The fort is located at great depth and appears to be about 3,000 years old.¹⁶⁰

Shi Cheng

Of course, not to be outdone, China has (at least) one deep Lake buried city. Shi Cheng the “Lion City” is located at a depth of 130 feet. It is a thousands of years old city that was lost because it was buried by a modern reservoir, in 1959.¹⁶¹

This is proof that after only 50-60 years, as generations grow older and die, it will be quite easy to eliminate memory of anything even as large as a city.

Fuyuan City

The remains of Fuyuan are also of legend. They are located in Fuxian Lake, and although ancient are quite historical. Once again, despite record-keeping, it doesn't seem that many people know about or understand the city and what happened to it.¹⁶²

There are rumors of the city having ruins, pyramids, and palaces. But despite being in a lake, and not out in the middle of the ocean, the city remains quite enigmatic and difficult to study. How much more so would be a lost continent and city?

Caspian Sea

Perhaps everywhere has its own lost city culture. However, in the case of the Caspian Sea, it seems very likely to not only be lost, but remain lost.¹⁶³ Any cities that sank into this large inland lake will remain almost certainly buried, at least until the political and social situations surrounding this area improve and there are a plethora of local archaeologists who are willing to explore the depths. Could they find evidence of Tepe Period or earlier inhabitants, and civilizations? Maybe, but the likelihood at the moment seems quite low.¹⁶⁴

Iceland, the future Atlantis?

It would be remiss of the author not to mention that Iceland has been mentioned as a possible Atlantean future myth in the making, or in very odd circles, the past Atlantis,¹⁶⁵ moved due to crustal displacement. Iceland is located along the Mid-Atlantic Ridge, and like the Azores before, will share such a fate, in time. Sudden or slowly, Iceland's landmass is destined to sink beneath the waves, and become yet another island lost to the tides of history.

¹⁵⁹ <https://news.nationalgeographic.com/2017/11/underwater-fortress-urartu-lake-van-turkey-archaeology-video-spd/>

¹⁶⁰ <https://www.sciencealert.com/lake-van-turkey-3-000-year-old-sunken-castle-discovered-urartu>

¹⁶¹ <https://www.dailystar.co.uk/travel/travel-news/487595/Underwater-city-best-diving-spot-China-Shi-Cheng-Lion-City>

¹⁶² https://www.theepochtimes.com/enigmatic-carvings-on-underwater-ruins-in-china-mystify-investigators_1729925.html

¹⁶³ <http://mysteriousuniverse.org/2015/04/the-strange-mysteries-of-the-caspian-sea/>

¹⁶⁴ Just like a volcanic atoll, the paper rises to a crescendo, and retreats mysteriously back into obscurity, leaving us with wonder and confusion.

¹⁶⁵ <https://www.juneastin.co.uk/ancient-civilisations/iceland-atlantis>

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Appendix

Table 3 - Ancient Megalith Size and Weight Comparisons, top 50 sites.¹⁶⁶

Location	Stone Name	Weight (s. tons)	Length (feet)	Width/Diameter (feet)	Depth/Thickness (feet)
Yangshan Quarry	Yangshan Stele	9699.2	162	35.1	14.4
Baalbek	Unnamed Monolith 1	1818.8	64.3	19.7	18.04
Baalbek	Unnamed Monolith 2	1369.1	67.3	16.4	14.75
Aswan	The Unfinished Obelisk	1212.5	137	14.4	8.2
Baalbek	Stone of the Pregnant Woman	1102.3	66.6	14.75	13.9
Thebes	Ramesseum	1102	75		
Mangi Tungi, India	Statue of Ahimsa	990	108		
Madhyah Pradesh	Bawangaja	882	84		
Baalbek	Trilithon	882	70	14	10
Thebes	Colossi of Memnon	771.6	60		
Shravanabelagola, India	Gommateshwara	661	60	30	
Axum, Ethiopia	Great Stele	573	108		
Jerusalem	Western Stone, Holy Temple	569.9	44.6	9.8	10.8
Giza	Great Pyramid Temple	441			
Asuka, Japan	Masuda no Iwafune	440.9	36	26.2	15.4
Locmariaquer, Brittany	The Broken Menhir of Er Grah	363.8	67.6		
Karnak, Egypt	Obelisk of Karnak	328			
Alexandria	Pompey's Pillar	314.2	67.1	8.89	
Gwalior Fort	Rishabha Statue	300	58.4		
Ravenna, Italy	Mausoleum of Theodoric	253.5	3	32.8	
Gochang, Korea	Ganghwa Dolmen	248.2	23.2	18	8.5
Giza	Menkaure's Pyramid stone	242.5			
Mons Claudianus, Egypt	Granite Column	228.2	59		
Luxor, Egypt	Luxor Obelisk	227			
Saqqara	Sahure's Pyramid Stone	220.5			
Giza	Foundation Stones	200	26	19	7.5
Antequarra, Spain	Menga Dolmen	198.4			
Axum, Ethiopia	King Ezana's Stele	187.4	69		
Coatlinchan, Mexico	Statue of Tlaloc	168			
Brittany, France	Kerloas Menhir	150			

¹⁶⁶ Map: <https://www.google.com/maps/@1.1476503,-72.3674353,3z/data=!3m1!4b1!4m2!6m1!1s1!tUEGd3r3uXXuQaQVCIAzbpz-0pi5DqO>

Saqqara, Egypt	Khendjer Pyramid	150			
Axum, Ethiopia	Obelisk of Axum	132.3	79		
Tiwanaku, Bolivia	Ashlars	130			
Cusco, Peru	Sacsayhuamán	125			
Mycenae, Greece	Treasury of Atreus	120	27.2	17.1	3.9
Carlow, Ireland	Brownshill Dolmen	110.2			
Hawara, Egypt	Pyramid of Amenemhet III	110			
Ollantaytambo, Peru	Six large stones	100			
Rome	Baths of Caracalla	100			
Istanbul, Turkey	Hagia Sophia	100			
Easter Island	Moai	90.4	33		
Nyuserre Ini	Nyuserre Pyramid	90	32.8		
Rome	Trajan's Column	84.9	98	12.1	
Asuka, Japan	Ishibatai Kofun	75			
Rome, Italy	Pantheon Columns	60	39	5	
Malta Temple	Ħaġar Qim	57	19	9	2
Stonehenge	Largest Trilithon Sarsen Stone	50	29		
Vaishali, India	Ashoka Pillars	50	50		
Gobekli Tepe	Unfinished T-Pillar	50			
Olmec, Mexico	La Cobata	45	11	9.8	9.8

Figure 27 - Sorted by Size and color-coded¹⁶⁷

¹⁶⁷ Red *might be* descended from Atlantean OR Archaic period; Orange is Tepe Period (direct descendent culture of Atlanteans Period); Purple is [likely] from the cataclysmic age, possibly one or another period; Green is confirmed Venus to Mars cataclysm; Blue are, for the most part Historic-Ancient and Megalithic Period, Dynastic times, or the Transition Period of religious movement. As can be seen there is no discernable pattern between age and size, despite usual assertions from catastrophist and diffusionist parties. Several of the red pillars all belong to Baalbek.